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Report on MIRRI-Innovative services survey

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1. INTRODUCTION

Objectives of the survey:

This consultation is intended to gather input from our main stakeholders, being users of microbial resources, to shape the service output of MIRRI. The questions focus on several topics related to Microbial domain Biological Resource Centres (mBRCs) in which MIRRI can make a difference and improve the present situation for both profit and non-profit respondents.

The feedback will have an impact on the design and content of MIRRI as a new concept, with goals beyond what single mBRCs can offer individually, considering that MIRRI will be a portal facilitating access to microbial material, data, expertise, and services distributed in Europe.

Target groups of the survey:

- End-users of microbial resources in schools, universities, public or private institutes and bio-industry (e.g. Biotechnology, Agriculture, Food, Health, Energy & Climate, Environment)

2. METHODOLOGY

An online survey consisting of 40 questions was set up in English (Annex 1). Users participating in the survey had to agree with the terms laid down in the MIRRI Statement on Use, Access and Protection of Collected data (Annex 2).

Respondents were asked to evaluate the added value of MIRRI and to identify what improved or innovative services MIRRI could provide beyond what is currently offered by public mBRCs individually. To situate the answers of the respondent in the proper context, the current situation is indicated using *italic font*.

To reach respondents, MIRRI collections were asked to distribute the survey to their customers. Furthermore, one coordinator per country (MIRRI partner or Collaborating Party) was nominated as responsible to compile a list of contacts in the bio-industry (companies retrieved from public directories, associations, etc.) and to distribute the questionnaire to these (potential) users in their country. In addition, the Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) has been involved to approach the BioChemTech sector and other bioindustries in Europe. The questionnaire was also distributed via the social media and the MIRRI website. No data was gathered on the numbers of users reached by each distribution channel (mailings to current CC users or members of microbiological associations, or the EFB or MIRRI websites). Consequently, a response rate could not be calculated.

The online questionnaire was accessible from January 21st until June 30th 2014 during which, **982 responses** were received. Only 898 responses (91,4 %) were considered valid, i.e. these respondents stated to be involved in any way with microbial resources for their professional activities (they answered “Yes” to question 3). Only valid responses were taken for further analysis.

In the contact information section of the questionnaire (Annex 1), identification of the organisation was skipped by approximately 38.6 % respondents (347 anonymous replies), whereas 551 users (61.4 %) provided personal contact details and information on their function, organization, and laboratory unit. Hence, this latter group of users (66.1 % from the non-profit sector and 33.9 % from the profit sector), can be contacted again for additional information on their laboratory unit’s needs and expectations to represent the user community in the future development processes of MIRRI.

3. RESULTS

The percentages given in this summary report are calculated based on the number of respondents **per question** and not the total number of respondents of the survey, unless stated otherwise.

It is important to realize that respondents were given the opportunity to skip questions during the questionnaire, which explains the different total number of respondents for different questions. In addition, the user profile may not entirely reflect the user community, as some of the anonymous replies may come from people working in the same company or department.

If respondents were allowed to select several options that apply, this is indicated as “multiple answers”.

3.1. User profiles

3.1.1. Country of origin (Q2)

All respondents represented 63 different countries. 764 responses (85.1 %) originated from 30 different European countries (including the Russian Federation), while 134 (14.9 %) originated from 33 countries outside Europe.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the 764 respondents from **European countries** (including the Russian Federation) of which, 684 (89.5 %) originated from the host countries of one or more CCs that participate in the MIRRI preparatory phase project as a full partner (**bold**) or as a collaborating party and 80 (10.5 %) originated from thirteen other European countries without active MIRRI partners.

Table 1. Number of respondents and list of culture collections participating in MIRRI¹ from European countries and the Russian Federation

Country	Number of respondents	% of total respondents	List of CCs collaborating in the MIRRI preparatory phase project
Spain	287	32.0	CECT
Germany	109	12.1	DSMZ, SAG
Italy	61	6.8	MUT, ICLC, ITEM, DBVPG
France	33	3.7	CIP-CRBIP, CIRM-BIA, CIRM-BP, CIRM-CF, CIRM-CFBP, CIRM-Levures
The Netherlands	32	3.6	CBS
Portugal	30	3.3	MUM, PYCC
Belgium	27	3.0	BCCM-LMG, BCCM-IHEM, BCCM-LMBP, BCCM-MUCL
Switzerland	27	3.0	-
UK	20	2.2	CABI, NCIMB
Denmark	19	2.1	-
Czech Republic	13	1.4	CCF
Sweden	13	1.4	CCUG
Greece	13	1.4	ACA-DC, ATHUM
Austria	12	1.3	-
Turkey	11	1.2	-
Finland	9	1.0	VTTCC
Poland	9	1.0	IAFB, PCM
Hungary	8	0.9	NCAIM
Bulgaria	7	0.8	-
Ireland	6	0.7	-
Russian Federation	4	0.4	VKM, IEGM
Slovakia	3	0.3	CCY
Norway	2	0.2	-
Slovenia	2	0.2	-
Serbia	2	0.2	-
Croatia	1	0.1	-
Estonia	1	0.1	-
Iceland	1	0.1	-
Luxembourg	1	0.1	-
Romania	1	0.1	-
Latvia	0	0.0	MSCL
Responses from 30 countries	764	85.1	

¹CCs that are full partners in MIRRI are in bold, the others are collaborating parties. See Annex 3 for full name and details of CCs participating in the MIRRI preparatory phase.

Table 2 shows the distribution of the 134 respondents from **countries outside Europe**: 62 from Asia, 52 from South- or North-America, 13 from Africa and 7 from Australia and Oceania.

Table 2. Number of respondents from countries outside Europe

Non-European countries	Number of respondents	% of total respondents	Region or continent
United States	25	2.5	North-America
China	18	1.8	Asia
India	13	1.3	Asia
Brazil	6	0.6	South-America
South-Korea	6	0.6	Asia
Chile	5	0.5	South-America
Thailand	5	0.5	Asia
South-Africa	5	0.5	Africa
Canada	4	0.4	North-America
Egypt	4	0.4	Africa
Mexico	4	0.4	North-America
New Zealand	4	0.4	Australia and Oceania
Argentina	3	0.3	South-America
Australia	3	0.3	Australia and Oceania
Iran	3	0.3	Asia
Japan	3	0.3	Asia
Singapore	3	0.3	Asia
Israel	2	0.2	Asia
Saudi Arabia	2	0.2	Asia
Sudan	2	0.2	Africa
Vietnam	2	0.2	Asia
Bolivia	1	0.1	South-America
Colombia	1	0.1	South-America
Ecuador	1	0.1	South-America
Georgia	1	0.1	Asia
Indonesia	1	0.1	Asia
Kuwait	1	0.1	Asia
Malaysia	1	0.1	Asia
Oman	1	0.1	Africa
Peru	1	0.1	South-America
Reunion	1	0.1	Africa
Taiwan	1	0.1	Asia
Uruguay	1	0.1	South-America
Responses from 33 countries	134	13.5	

3.1.2. Type of respondents (Q4-Q6)

The **non-profit** sector accounted for **594 respondents** (66.2 %), of which the majority were academics (76.3 %) followed by respondents from an environmental (23.5 %) or food & feed focussed sector (21.5 %), whether or not in combination with (an)other type(s). Other organization types within the non-profit group were less represented: Agronomy (13 %), Pharma & Medical (12.5 %), Diagnostic (11.8 %), Bioremediation (11.4 %), Chemical (8.5 %), Quality Analytical Lab (8.4 %), Veterinary (6.7 %) and Cosmetics (2.4 %) (Table 3). Other organization types mentioned were e.g. Governmental and international research institutes, Associations and Biological resource or technical centres.

The **profit** sector accounted for **302 respondents** (38.8 %), of which the majority represented small to medium size enterprises, corresponding to 42.5 % of all respondents. Large enterprises and micro-enterprises represented respectively, 30.2 % and 27.2 % of all respondents. Most profit respondents were active in Food & feed (42.8 %), Pharma & Medical (30.3 %) or Quality Analytical Lab (26.3 %) oriented fields (Figure 1).

Table 3. Number of respondents per organization type (non-profit sector) or per size (profit sector) (multiple answers allowed for the organization type within the non-profit sector)

Sector	Organization type(s) (non-profit) or size of the enterprise (profit)	Number of respondents	% within sector	% of all respondents (N = 898)
Non-profit Answered: 592	Academic & Education	447	76.3	49.8
	Environmental	138	23.5	15.4
	Food & Feed	126	21.5	14.0
	Agronomy	76	13.0	8.5
	Pharma & Medical	73	12.5	8.1
	Diagnostic	69	11.8	7.7
	Bioremediation	67	11.4	7.5
	Chemical	50	8.5	5.6
	Quality Analytical Lab	49	8.4	5.5
	Veterinary	39	6.7	4.3
	Cosmetics	14	2.4	1.6
Profit Answered: 302	Small to Medium size enterprise (10-250 employees)	128	42.5	14.3
	Large enterprise (>250 employees)	91	30.2	10.2
	Micro-enterprise (< 10 employees)	82	27.2	9.2

3.2. The MIRRI offer: “What MIRRI can do differently?”

3.2.1. User preferences about potential mBRC offered services

Most respondents, 67.6% within the **non-profit** user group and 63.6 % within the profit group, indicated to be current users of microbial resources or related services provided by mBRCs (Q7).

To rate the user preferences about the potential MIRRI offer, respondents were asked to provide their feeling (level of impact or degree of usefulness) to a number of statements. This rating scale question type allows to calculate a weighted average based on the weight assigned to each answer choice. The rating averages were calculated by multiplying the weighted value of each rating with the actual number of respondents who picked that rating, adding the totals and dividing it by the number of ratings given. Table 4 shows a summary of the user responses about their interest in potential mBRCs services.

(1) Search for microbial resources and associated data (Q8-9)

At the moment, customers have to navigate through different catalogues and contact different mBRCs in their search for specific microbial resources. In addition, the mBRC catalogues and databases generally provide non-integrated and sometimes inconsistent or incorrect data. MIRRI not only proposes to set up a unique search tool, covering all microbial resources offered by the participating European mBRCs, it also aims to integrate and curate microbial resource data from participating European mBRCs and other online sources (e.g. publications, genomic data).

The **non-profit** respondent group indicated an integrated search tool as a major improvement (74.2 %) in comparison with the **profit** group (61.0 %) (Figure 2).

Overall, both **non-profit** and **profit** indicated this unique and integrated search tool for mBRCs as an improvement with a rating average of respectively 3.6 and 3.5, which is between “is only a minor improvement” and “is a major improvement”.

In addition, 81.7 % of the **non-profit** group indicated this MIRRI offer of an integrated and curated database to be a major improvement, and 68.7 % of the **profit** respondents shared this opinion (Figure 3). Overall rating averages for both **non-profit** and **profit** sector were between “is only a minor improvement” and “is a major improvement” (respectively 3.7 and 3.6).

Although both sectors (profit and non-profit) declare to see an improvement in having integrated and curated search tools and databases these are mostly required by the non-profit sector, which accounted 13 % more respondents indicating these services as major improvements.

(2) Relevance of microbial resources related information (Q10-Q11)

Above 50 % of the user community consider all the proposed items as very useful information for their work, with the exception of related patents, which is “of little use” or “of no use” for 60 % of the **non-profit** respondents.

Both **profit** and **non-profit** consider biotechnological applications and related patents the less important information (Table 4). In addition to these, the **profit** group also placed habitat and environmental information, genomic data and physiology and metabolism among the lower ranked types of information. Conversely, information regarding growth conditions and requirements, pathogenicity, taxonomy and classification and literature references were considered as very useful (rating average of approximately 3) by a **profit** point of view.

In general, the **non-profit** sector considers most types of information more useful for their work, as the percentage of respondents that indicated “very useful” is above 10 % in comparison with the **profit** respondents for the same items. Exception to this general rule are growth conditions and requirements, pathogenicity and biotechnological applications, which show similar percentages in both sectors, and related patent information, which is more useful for the **profit** sector. The biggest difference between both sectors is found in the genomic data related information, which is one of the highest ranked by the non-profit sector (2.7) and one of the lowest ranked by the profit sector (2.4).

Figure 4 gives an overview of the percentages within each user group (profit or non-profit) that indicated whether the proposed information is either “very useful”, “of little use”, or “of no use” for their work. Several respondents indicated other information as relevant for their work (answers listed in Annex 4).

Figure 4: Relevance of microbial resources related information. The numbers indicate the % of profit (N = 273) or non-profit (N = 542) respondents that found the indicated information either very useful, of little use or of no use.

Figure 5 shows a word cloud analysis of databases that users consider important for their work, which represents the 50 most important words and phrases mentioned by respondents. The cloud gives greater prominence to words that appeared more frequently. The numbers indicate how many of the respondents (N=410 respondents) mentioned the word. As shown, users indicated that they would like MIRRI to establish a direct link to other collections (ATCC, DSMZ, CECT, ...) and databases such as NCBI, GenBank, StrainInfo, Pubmed, A complete list of all responses to the question “List existing databases that are very useful for your work, and to which MIRRI could establish a direct link.” is found in Annex 5.

Figure 5: Word cloud representation about user preferences for existing databases (N = 410).

(3) Quality of material provided by mBRCs (Q12-Q13)

MIRRI wants to set up criteria to assure a standardized high quality of microbial resources offered by participating European mBRCs. In total, 95.4 % of the respondents indicated that a standardized and high quality of resources offered by mBRCs would be an improvement (Figure 6). More specifically, 70.4 % of the **profit** group and 74.5 % of the **non-profit** respondents rated this MIRRI offer as a major improvement (Figure 6).

In addition to the quality of the material, the majority of both **profit** (58.1 %) and **non-profit** (53.9 %) respondents preferred that mBRCs are formally certified or accredited and for about 1/4th (27.3 % of the **profit** group and 22.4 % of the **non-profit**) this is a mandatory criteria (Figure 7).

(4) Ordering material from mBRCs (Q14-Q16)

The combination of the search tool with an integrated one-stop shop was generally considered as an improvement (91.3 % of the respondents) although the **non-profit** sector (69.1 %) was more convinced of this offer as a major improvement than the **profit** sector (56.9 %) (Figure 8).

This one-stop shop would allow customers to search and order resources from different participating European mBRCs, but Material Transfer Agreements can differ in several respects. For this reason, MIRRI proposes in support of the one-stop shop, to harmonize the conditions for access to, and (commercial) use of, the microbial resources. In agreement with the response on the one-stop shop principle, the proposal was generally indicated to be an improvement (92.7 %) (Figure 9). In this case, the differences between the **non-profit** (66.6 %) and the **profit** sector (61.5 %) are less pronounced (Figure 9).

When the order is made through the one-stop shop, the material will be shipped by the respective mBRCs involved. Regarding invoicing such a split order, 66.1 % within the **profit** respondents and 67.1 % within the **non-profit** sector respondents found it acceptable that each shipment is accompanied by a corresponding invoice (Figure 10).

(5) Deposit of material at mBRCs (Q17)

A system directing depositors to the participating European mBRCs suitable for the specific material to be deposited, was generally considered as an improvement. In total 57.0 % of the **non-profit** and 43.0 % of the **profit** respondents rated the deposit guidance system as a major improvement (Figure 11).

(6) Offer of microbial materials at mBRCs (Q18-Q22)

Currently, supply of microbial cultures is mainly as pure cultures, individually preserved, and of unknown count. Both **profit** (84.7 %) and **non-profit** (86.6 %) respondents indicated that the implementation of new technologies to offer microbial materials in alternative formats would be an improvement for their work (Figure 12).

Given several options regarding alternative formats, both **profit** and **non-profit** users indicated that a single culture with known colony forming units was very relevant for their purposes (rating average of 2.5 and 2.6; Table 4), while the other options (mixed culture with known composition; large scale inoculum, permanent microscopy slide set and specific purpose strain panel) were rated only of little use.

Other relevant formats mentioned by respondents were easy to resurrect, lyophilized and more DNA/RNA related issues (a complete list of all other formats is given in Annex 6).

*Requirements for highly specialized cultivation and/or preservation conditions are very often the limiting factor for authentic and publicly available microbial resources. MIRRI offers to enhance the capacity of the participating European mBRCs. This enhancement will be achieved via new expertise and implementation of new technologies to cultivate and preserve recalcitrant/ fastidious microorganisms currently not covered by these mBRCs. The enhanced capacity is generally well appreciated as 88.2 % of the respondents considers this offer to be an improvement (Figure 13). About half of the **profit** sector (53.2 %) indicated this would be a major improvement, while 65.4 % of the **non-profit** sector considers this offer to be a major improvement (Figure 13).*

In addition to an enhanced capacity, MIRRI will encourage specialized laboratories to associate with MIRRI. This way specialized collections of microbial resources will become accessible for the scientific community, in compliance with the MIRRI criteria.

Broadening the scope of offered material into the public domain, in compliance with the MIRRI criteria, is considered an improvement by 91.6 % of all respondents (Figure 13). Despite the fact that the overall feeling regarding this offer is similar for both profit and non-profit groups, the **non-profit** users (72.6%) are a bit more persuaded by the offer than **profit** users (63.5 %) (Figure 14).

When asked which organisms users would like to see taken up in the future offer, the answers were quite divers. To visualize the most common responses a word cloud analysis was performed (Figure 15).Users indicated among others several plant pathogens such as phytophthora species and Xylella

fastidiosa. Especially, this latter was found to be very restricted by public *mBRCs*. (A complete list of all top three microorganism responses is listed in Annex 7).

Figure 15: Word cloud representation about user requirements for microbial resources (N = 518).

(7) Services in microbiology provided by mBRCs (Q23-Q28)

Aside from microbial resources, Microbial Resource Centres very often offer services in microbiology. Despite changing needs of academics and bio-industry, only 35.6 % of both fields claims that additional mBRC services are necessary. Both **profit** (62.6 %) and **non-profit** (65.3 %) respondents consider the services currently offered by mBRCs sufficient.

Although 64.4 % of all respondents is generally pleased with the current service offer, *an integrated search tool covering the services offered by the participating European mBRCs* is considered an improvement by 94.6 % of the **non-profit** users and 94.1 % of the **profit** respondents (Figure 16). In agreement with the one-stop shop for resources, a one-stop shop for services is also considered as an improvement by 92.0 % of all respondents (Figure 17). In support of this one-stop shop, MIRRI proposes to harmonize the service agreements concluded between the participating European mBRCs and their customers. About half of the **profit** respondents (53.8 %) agrees that uniform service agreements will be a major improvement for their work, while an even higher part of the **non-profit** sector (61.2 %) claims this statement (Figure 18).

Both users groups were asked to indicate the relevance of certain potential new services. In total 81.3 % to 81.5 % of all respondents indicated that both customized preservation and cultivation of microorganisms would be very useful for their work (Table 4). Closely followed by customized isolation of microorganisms. Supply of cDNA or specific amplified genes, organization of proficiency tests were generally rated less interesting.

Several respondents listed new services to increase the efficiency of the MIRRI service output (a complete overview is listed in Annex 8). A word cloud representation (Figure 19) of given responses show, among others, sequencing related issues as the most interesting. However, the most relevant comments were actually applying to the financial aspect of the offered services, as users consider too expensive services as unattractive. In addition, several users emphasized the importance of preservation (strains/species cited in old literature are no longer available) and strain authentication.

Figure 19: Word cloud representation about user proposed new services.

(8) Expertise available from Microbial Resource Centres (Q29-Q33)

MIRRI proposes to set up unique expert platforms, offering access to the combined expertise of specialists from within and outside European mBRCs. This facilitated access to advice, consultancy or

training on matters related to microbial materials is regarded as an improvement by 92.5 % of the **non-profit** respondents and 92.7 % of the **profit** group (figure 20).

When users were asked to rate potential expert platforms, both **profit** and **non-profit** indicated that the set-up of level 1, level 2 or level 3 facilities would be only of little use (rating average of 1.5 and 1.4 respectively). Although both sectors generally rated the proposed platforms as very useful (rating average RA above 1.5; see Table4), there were two topics on which there was no conformity. While the **non-profit** indicated information technology (including data analysis) as very useful, the **profit** sector rated this lower (Table 4). On the other hand, the **profit** users claim that expert platforms focussing on legal matters (including intellectual property rights and benefit sharing) are very useful, while the **non-profit** sector believes this is only of little use.

Regarding access to the expertise offered by the platforms, both sectors prefer on-line guides, documents, presentations, searchable databases with individual experts per subject and collaborations (Table 4). On-site access either in group or at individual level at mBRCs or on-site access at the organization are considered the least desired access options (Table 4).

It is fundamental for an efficient expert service output that MIRRI focusses on the involvement of its stakeholders in the further development of the infrastructure. To improve the dialogue between mBRCs and their user communities, 36.9 % of the **non-profit** users and 32.5 % of the **profit** respondents is willing to act as an expert from their sector/field of expertise (Table 5). In total, only 24.0 % of all respondents indicated they do not want to be an expert. This means that there are still some potential experts among the **profit** (45.6 %) and **non-profit** (38.0 %) respondents that are still doubting.

Annex 9 gives an overview of all respondents that wish to act as experts and their respective field of expertise (Q32-33). The fields of expertise include quite diverse sectors including: general microbiology, biotechnology, food & feed, agronomy, Chemical, environmental, mycology...

Table 4: Weighted average responses to the questions about potential mBRC offered services. The rating averages were calculated by multiplying the weighted value of each rating with the actual number of respondents who picked that rating, adding the totals and dividing it by the number of ratings given.

Rating average about the impact of improved services (scale 1-4; “is a major improvement” or “is very useful”= 4; “is only a minor improvement” or “is only of little use” = 3; “has no impact” = 2 or “ is a drawback” = 1)	Rate (profit)	Rate (non-profit)
Integrated search tool of microbial resources	3.5	3.6
Integrated and curated database of microbial resources	3.6	3.7
Standardized and high quality microbial resources	3.6	3.7
One stop-shop for microbial resources	3.5	3.6
Harmonized conditions for access and use	3.5	3.6
Deposit guide to identify the appropriate mBRC for depositing	3.3	3.5
Alternative formats for strain supply	3.3	3.3
Broadened offer: resources difficult to cultivate and/or preserve	3.4	3.6
Broadened offer: resources difficult to find	3.6	3.7
Integrated search tool of microbiology-related services	3.6	3.7
One stop-shop for microbiology-related services	3.5	3.6
Uniform service agreements	3.4	3.5
Facilitated access to expertise in microbiology	3.6	3.6
Rating average about the usefulness of services (scale 1-3; “is very useful” = 3; “is only of little use” = 2 and “ is of no use” = 1)	Rate (profit)	Rate (non-profit)
Relevance of microbial resources related information		
growth conditions and requirements	2.8	2.9
taxonomy and classification	2.6	2.8
literature references	2.6	2.7
genomic data, including sequences	2.4	2.7
physiology and metabolism	2.5	2.7
habitat and environmental information	2.5	2.6
pathogenicity	2.7	2.6
biotechnological applications	2.4	2.5
related patents	2.3	2.2
Alternative formats for strain supply		
Single culture with known Colony Forming Units	2.6	2.6
Mixed culture with known composition	1.9	1.9

Specific purpose strain panel	1.9	1.8
Large scale inoculum	1.7	1.6
Permanent microscopy slide set	1.6	1.6
Rating average about the usefulness of services (scale 1-2; "is very useful" = 2 or "is only of little use" = 1)	Rate (profit)	Rate (non-profit)
Relevance of proposed new services		
customized preservation of microorganisms	1.5	1.7
customized cultivation of microorganisms	1.6	1.6
screening for specific genes, enzymes, metabolites, or other features	1.5	1.6
customized isolation of microorganisms	1.6	1.6
primer design for specific target sequences	1.5	1.5
supply of specific amplified genes	1.4	1.5
data analysis and interpretation	1.5	1.5
supply of cDNA	1.4	1.5
organization of proficiency tests or ring tests	1.5	1.4
Interest in suggested expert platforms		
isolation and cultivation of microorganisms	1.7	1.7
preservation of microbial resources	1.7	1.6
microbial taxonomy and identification, including related technology	1.7	1.6
applied microbiology, including screening technology	1.6	1.5
information technology, including data analysis	1.6	1.5
legal matters related to access, distribution, and (commercial) use of microbial resources, including Intellectual Property Rights and Benefit Sharing	1.5	1.6
biosafety and biosecurity	1.6	1.6
set-up of Level 1, Level 2 or Level 3 facilities	1.5	1.4
Interest in different formats regarding access to expertise platforms		
on-line guides, documents, presentations	1.8	1.9
searchable database with individual experts per subject	1.7	1.8
collaboration in fundamental or applied research projects	1.5	1.7
symposia and workshops	1.5	1.5
webinars	1.5	1.4
on-site at the relevant mBRCs, in group with other interested persons	1.4	1.5
on-site at the relevant mBRCs, on individual basis	1.4	1.4

on-site at your organization	1.3	1.4
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3.2.2. Further communication with relation to MIRRI (Q38-Q40)

In total 86.7 % of all respondents answered positive when asked if they would like to be further informed about MIRRI’s activities. Both **profit** and **non-profit** users prefer to be informed about these further activities via email (respectively 86.2 % and 85.9 %). Other preferred communication channels were e-newsletter (28.3 % and 20.9 %) or the MIRRI website (12.6 % and 14.7 %).

In the past, the majority of both **profit** and **non-profit** users learned about MIRRI via the present questionnaire (46.5 % and 43.8 %). The top three of communication channels that made users aware of MIRRI is completed by mail (respectively 24.8 % and 22.6 %) and the previous questionnaire (16.8 % and 21.9 %).

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- The proposed MIRRI offer related to resources supply by mBRCs were generally considered as “major improvements” or “very useful” by the majority of the respondents (rating average at or above 3.5, scale 1-4; Table 4). Among non-profit users only “alternative formats of strain supply” was rated at 3.3 (Table 4), which is closer to “is a minor improvement”. The profit sector shows the same opinion about this service, and both sectors agree that only “Single culture with known Colony Forming Units” would be a format of strain supply useful for their work (rating average 2.6, scale 1-3, Table 4). Several respondents have indicated microorganisms groups that are currently not easily found. Some are already available within MIRRI mBRCs so they will become more visible via the MIRRI portal. Others are still missing and should be gradually incorporated as part of the MIRRI policy to broaden the offer.
- Regarding the MIRRI data offer all proposed related information seem to be very relevant for the users (rating average at or above 2.5, scale 1-3; Table 4), with the exception of related patents, which is of lesser use for the majority of respondents. Information about biotechnological applications and genomic data (including sequences) are also less important for the profit sector (rating average 2.4, scale 1-3; Table 4). Users have suggested several databases that are important for their work, to establish a direct link to them should be part of the MIRRI strategy.
- New or less common microbial services, such as customized isolation, cultivation or preservation of microorganisms, or screening for specific genes, enzymes, metabolites, or other features, are considered also very useful by the user community (rating average above 1.5, scale 1-2; Table 4). In addition, respondents have suggested other services that would be useful for their work, like mutant construction, pathogenicity analyses, etc. MIRRI should work towards the possibility of offering these services.
- Users would find very useful the creation of expert topic-driven platforms. All suggested topics are interesting for the respondents (rating average at or above 1.5, scale 1-2; Table 4) with the only exception of setting up Level 1, 2 or 3 facilities, which is less relevant for non-profit users (rate = 1.4, table 4). The preferred formats to access to these expertise is on the first place via on-line guides, documents and presentations, second through a searchable database with individual experts per subject and third collaborating in fundamental or applied research projects. Webinars and on-site access at the mBRCs are the less rated approaches to receive expert services. MIRRI should create such searchable expert platforms and produce documents and guides about relevant microbial resources related topics.
- Users are willing to participate in the MIRRI platform as experts to improve the dialogue between mBRCs and their user communities.

- This information should be shared with work packaged 6 as they are currently generating expert list in different fields.
- The role of an expert in MIRRI should be clearly defined. A clear and straightforward description covering the rights and obligations of the expert could convince potential experts in both the profit and non-profit sector to act as an expert. Perhaps, a differentiation between internal (mBRCs staff) and external experts should be established and defined.

Overall, the responses to this survey clearly indicate that both profit and non-profit users believe in an efficient decentralised infrastructure which provides users with optimal resources and related information, services and expertise. This broad and uniform support should drive the creation of the MIRRI infrastructure and set up the basis for the construction phase.

5. ANNEXES

5.1. Annex 1: MIRRI-WP2 Innovative services questionnaire

Privacy Statement

1. Do you agree with the MIRRI Statement on Use, Access and Protection of collected data? [Y; N]

General information

2. In which country is your Organization located? *[drop-down list]*

3. Is your Organization involved in any way with microbial resources for its professional activities? *[Yes; No -> DISQUALIFIED, only respondents answering "Yes" are able to continue]*

4. To which sector does your Organization belong? *[Profit sector; Non-profit sector]*

5. What is the size of the enterprise? *[Micro-enterprise (less than 10 employees); Small to Medium size enterprise (between 10 and 250 employees); Large enterprise (more than 250 employees)]*

6. In which field(s) is your Organization active? *[Academic & Education; Quality Analytical Lab; Pharma & Medical; Veterinary; Agronomy; Food & Feed; Chemical; Cosmetics; Diagnostic; Bioremediation; Environmental; Other (specify)]*

7. Are you a current user of the microbial resources or related services provided by public Microbial Resource Centres (mBRCs)? *[Y; N]*

Search for microbial resources and associated data provided by Microbial Resource Centres (mBRCs)

SITUATION AT PRESENT	WHAT MIRRI CAN DO DIFFERENTLY	WE VALUE YOUR OPINION
To search for specific microbial resources, customers have to navigate through different catalogues and contact different mBRCs.	MIRRI proposes to set up a unique search tool, covering all microbial resources offered by the participating European mBRCs.	8. For my work such unique and integrated search tool for mBRC catalogues <i>[is a major improvement; is only a minor improvement; has no impact; is a drawback; is not applicable]</i>
mBRC catalogues and public databases on microorganisms generally provide non-integrated and sometimes inconsistent or incorrect data.	MIRRI will aim to integrate and curate microbial resource data that is available from participating European mBRCs (e.g. growth conditions, properties) and other online sources (e.g. publications, genomic data).	9. For my work such integrated and curated database <i>[is a major improvement; is only a minor improvement; has no impact; is a drawback; is not applicable]</i>

ANNEX 2: MIRRI Statement

10. For each of the following types of information related to microbial resources, please indicate the relevance for your work: *[taxonomy and classification; habitat and environmental information; growth conditions and requirements; physiology and metabolism; pathogenicity; genomic data, including sequences; biotechnological applications; related patents; literature references; Other information types (specify)]*

- very useful
- only of little use
- of no use
- not applicable

11. Please list existing databases that are very useful for your work, and to which MIRRI could establish a direct link. [free text]

Quality of material provided by public Microbial Resource Centres (mBRCs)

SITUATION AT PRESENT	WHAT MIRRI CAN DO DIFFERENTLY	WE VALUE YOUR OPINION
Although many mBRCs have a quality management system in place, the extent to which the quality of the resources (i.e. viability, identification, authenticity) is checked may differ considerably.	MIRRI wants to set up criteria assuring a standardized high quality of the microbial resources offered by the participating European mBRCs.	<p>12. For my work a standardized and high quality of resources offered by mBRCs</p> <p><i>[is a major improvement; is only a minor improvement; has no impact; is a drawback; is not applicable]</i></p>

13. Do the mBRCs need to be formally certified or accredited in order to be a supplier of microbial material for your work? *[this is mandatory; this is preferred; this is not necessary]*

ANNEX 2: MIRRI Statement

Ordering material from public Microbial Resource Centres (mBRCs)

SITUATION AT PRESENT	WHAT MIRRI CAN DO DIFFERENTLY	WE VALUE YOUR OPINION
To order microbial resource samples offered by different mBRCs, customers have to navigate through different websites and contact the different mBRCs.	MIRRI proposes to complement the unique search tool with a unique one-stop shop, allowing customers to search and order resources from the different participating European mBRCs.	14. For my work such one-stop shop for ordering microbial materials <i>[is a major improvement; is only a minor improvement; has no impact; is a drawback; is not applicable]</i>
mBRCs have Material Transfer Agreements that can differ in several respects.	In support of the one-stop shop, MIRRI proposes to harmonize the conditions for access to, and (commercial) use of, the microbial resources offered by the participating European mBRCs.	15. For my work harmonized conditions for access and use <i>[are a major improvement; are only a minor improvement; have no impact; are a drawback; are not applicable]</i>

16. When the order is made through the one-stop shop, the material will be shipped by the respective mBRCs involved in the order. Regarding invoicing such a split order, what is required by your organization? *[One compiling invoice per order will be mandatory; It is acceptable that each shipment is accompanied by a corresponding invoice]*

Deposit of material at public Microbial Resource Centres (mBRCs)

SITUATION AT PRESENT	WHAT MIRRI CAN DO DIFFERENTLY	WE VALUE YOUR OPINION
Scientists willing or obliged to deposit microbial material at public mBRCs (i.e. for publication), encounter problems to identify the appropriate mBRCs.	MIRRI proposes to set up a unique guidance system, directing depositors to the participating European mBRCs suitable for the specific material to be deposited.	17. For my work such deposit guide <i>[is a major improvement; is only a minor improvement; has no impact; is a drawback; is not applicable]</i>

ANNEX 2: MIRRI Statement

Offer of microbial materials at Microbial Resource Centres (mBRCs)

SITUATION AT PRESENT	WHAT MIRRI CAN DO DIFFERENTLY	WE VALUE YOUR OPINION
Supply of microbial cultures is mainly as pure cultures, individually preserved, and of unknown count.	MIRRI will gain new expertise and implement new technologies to offer microbial materials in alternative formats.	18. For my work alternative formats of supply <i>[are a major improvement; are only a minor improvement; have no impact; are a drawback; are not applicable]</i>

19. For each of the following formats, please indicate the relevance for your work. *[Single culture with known Colony Forming Units; Mixed culture with known composition; Specific purpose strain panel (e.g. in microtiter plates); Large scale inoculum; Permanent microscopy slide set; Other formats (specify)]*

- very useful
- only of little use
- of no use
- not applicable

SITUATION AT PRESENT	WHAT MIRRI CAN DO DIFFERENTLY	WE VALUE YOUR OPINION
Gaps in authentic and publicly available microbial resources are often due to requirements for highly specialized cultivation and/or preservation conditions.	MIRRI will gain new expertise and implement new technologies to successfully cultivate and preserve recalcitrant/ fastidious microorganisms currently not covered by the participating European mBRCs.	20. For my work this enhanced capacity of mBRCs
Next to public mBRCs, specialized collections of microbial resources exist, but are kept at laboratories of universities or other scientific centres, and remain inaccessible for the scientific community.	MIRRI will encourage specialized laboratories to associate with MIRRI for bringing this material into the public domain, in compliance with the MIRRI criteria.	21. For my work broadening the scope of offered material <i>[is a major improvement; is only a minor improvement; has no impact; is a drawback; is not applicable]</i>

22. Please list the top three of microorganism groups important for your work but at present not offered by public mBRCs. *[free text]*

Services in microbiology provided by Microbial Resource Centres (mBRCs)

ANNEX 2: MIRRI Statement

SITUATION AT PRESENT	WHAT MIRRI CAN DO DIFFERENTLY	WE VALUE YOUR OPINION
To search for specific microbiology related analyses offered on a service basis by mBRCs, customers have to navigate through the different websites and contact the different mBRCs.	MIRRI proposes to set up a unique integrated search tool, covering the services offered by the participating European mBRCs.	23. For my work such integrated search tool for mBRC services <i>[is a major improvement; is only a minor improvement; has no impact; is a drawback; is not applicable]</i>
To order specific microbiology related analyses (services), customers have to contact different mBRCs.	MIRRI proposes to complement the service search tool with a unique one-stop shop, allowing customers to search and order services from mBRCs in different European countries.	24. For my work such one-stop shop for mBRC services <i>[is a major improvement; is only a minor improvement; has no impact; is a drawback; is not applicable]</i>
For comparable services, mBRCs and customers conclude Service Agreements which can differ in several respects.	In support of the one-stop shop, MIRRI proposes to harmonize the service agreements concluded between the participating European mBRCs and their customers.	25. For my work uniform service agreements <i>[are a major improvement; are only a minor improvement; have no impact; are a drawback; are not applicable]</i>
Changing needs of academics and bio-industry are not fully met by services in the portfolio of mBRCs. <i>An overview of the main services currently provided by most mBRCs can be viewed here.</i>	MIRRI will develop new services guided by the feedback received from academia and bio-industry.	26. For my work <i>[the services currently offered by mBRCs suffice; additional mBRC services are necessary]</i>

27. For each of the following suggestions for new services, please indicate the relevance for your work. *[customized isolation of microorganisms; customized cultivation of microorganisms, including media optimization; customized preservation of microorganisms; screening for specific genes, enzymes, metabolites, or other features; data analysis and interpretation; organization of proficiency tests or ring tests; primer design for specific target sequences; supply of specific amplified genes; supply of cDNA]*

- very useful
- only of little use
- of no use
- not applicable

28. It is fundamental for efficient service output that MIRRI focuses on new services that are required by the user community. Please list other new services that will be very useful for your work. *[free text]*

ANNEX 2: MIRRI Statement

Expertise available from Microbial Resource Centres (mBRCs)

SITUATION AT PRESENT	WHAT MIRRI CAN DO DIFFERENTLY	WE VALUE YOUR OPINION
In search for advice, consultancy or training on matters related to microbial materials, customers have to contact different mBRCs.	MIRRI proposes to set up unique expert platforms, offering customers access to the combined expertise of specialists from within and outside European mBRCs.	<p>29. For my work facilitated access to expertise in microbiology</p> <p><i>[is a major improvement; is only a minor improvement; has no impact; is a drawback; is not applicable]</i></p>

30. For each of the following subjects for these expert platforms please indicate the relevance for your work. *[microbial taxonomy and identification, including related technology; isolation and cultivation of microorganisms; preservation of microbial resources; applied microbiology, including screening technology; information technology, including data analysis; legal matters related to access, distribution, and (commercial) use of microbial resources, including Intellectual Property Rights and Benefit Sharing; biosafety and biosecurity; set-up of Level 1, Level 2 or Level 3 facilities; Other (specify)]*

- very useful
- only of little use
- of no use
- not applicable

31. Regarding access to the expertise offered by the platforms, please indicate your interest in each of following formats. *[searchable database with individual experts per subject; on-line guides, documents, presentations; webinars; symposia and workshops; on-site at the relevant mBRCs, on individual basis; on-site at the relevant mBRCs, in group with other interested persons; on-site at your organization; collaboration in fundamental or applied research projects]*

ANNEX 2: MIRRI Statement
Involvement of Microbial Resource Centre (mBRC) stakeholders

SITUATION AT PRESENT	WHAT MIRRI CAN DO DIFFERENTLY	WE VALUE YOUR OPINION
Dialogue between mBRCs and their User communities is limited.	MIRRI aims to involve its stakeholders in the further development of the Infrastructure and its envisaged output.	<p>32. Would you be interested to act as an expert from your sector?</p> <p><i>[yes, I am interested; no, I am not interested; I do not know at this moment]</i></p>

33. What is your field of expertise? *[free text]*

Contact information

34. Give the full name of your Organization. *[free text]*

35. Give the full name and complete address of your Laboratory unit. *[Full name; Address; City/Town; State/Province; ZIP/Postal Code; Country;*

36. Give your name, function, email address and phone number. *[Name; Function; Email Address; Phone Number]*

37. If different from the person filling in this questionnaire, give the name, function and contact information of the appropriate person to discuss your Organization's/Laboratory's future needs regarding microbial resources and related services. *[Name; Function; Email Address; Phone Number]*

Further communication with relation to MIRRI

38. How did you learn about MIRRI? *[Present questionnaire; Previous questionnaire; Colleagues; mBRCs supplying material or services; Press; Social Media; Conference; MIRRI website; Mail; Other (specify)]*

39. Would you like to be further informed about MIRRI's activities? [Y; N]

40. How do you prefer to be informed about MIRRI? *[email; e-newsletter; MIRRI website; Social Media; Workshops; Other (specify)]*

In 2013, MIRRI organized a survey to map the Users of microbial resources, being the prime stakeholder of the MIRRI initiative. In case you would be willing to complete this questionnaire (i.e. the User questionnaire, annex 3) as well, please click this [link](#). Otherwise, please click Done.

5.2. Annex 2: Statement on use, access and protection of collected data

Online survey to define the function and content of the Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure, MIRRI

1. What information will be collected, for what purpose and by what means?

MIRRI will provide means for efficient and coordinated access to microbial resources, associated data and new services in Europe. This survey is addressed to end-users of microbial materials and related services in **schools, universities, public or private institutes** and **bio-industry** (e.g. Biotechnology, Agriculture, Food, Health, Energy & Climate, Environment). The questionnaire inquires about their needs regarding coordinated operation of Microbial Resource Centres, new microbiological resources and services, training and consultancy, databases, quality and legal requirements, and their interest in the **portal** that MIRRI will establish.

The questionnaire is uploaded by means of an online application (SurveyMonkey®), which uses SSL encryption for secured data collection. The SurveyMonkey system uses session "cookies" in order to ensure communication between your PC and the server. Therefore, your browser must be configured to accept "cookies". However, SurveyMonkey does not collect personal or confidential information of any kind, nor any IP address from your PC.

The questionnaire can be completed anonymously if desired. Note that if you provide your personal contact details, the MIRRI consortium can contact you in the future for further consultation with regard to MIRRI.

2. Who has access to your information and to whom is it disclosed?

The raw data gathered in this survey will be transferred to a local database, which is accessible only to a strictly limited number of members of the MIRRI consortium responsible for the data analyses. Personal or company information as provided by the respondents will not be made public, and will be shared within the MIRRI consortium only to MIRRI partners on a need to know basis for further communication/contact in the frame of the MIRRI project.

The collected information will be delivered to the European Commission as a digested and anonymous output (Deliverable) of the MIRRI preparatory phase project.

ANNEX 2: MIRRI Statement

3. How do we protect and safeguard your information?

Access to the SurveyMonkey account is limited to the members of MIRRI Work Package 2, responsible for the upload of the questions and downloads of the responses, and is controlled via 'active directory authentication' (username and password). Access to the Personal Computer with the local database with raw data is limited to the system administrator and the local MIRRI research associates, and is controlled by username and password. Backups are made on an external device used only for this purpose, and will be deleted as described in (4).

4. How long do we keep your data?

Individual responses (raw data) will be deleted from databases at the latest one year after the digested output (Deliverable) has been reported to and accepted by the European Commission.

5. How can you access, verify, modify or delete your data?

Your responses can be accessed, completed or modified by yourself until the closure date of the consultation, as long as your session cookies remain saved on your computer (see point 1).

5.3. Annex 3: List of Culture Collections participating in the MIRRI preparatory phase project.

Culture Collection Acronym	Full name	Country	MIRRI status
ACA-DC	Agricultural University of Athens - Agricultural College of Athens - Dairy Collection	Greece	collaborating party
ATHUM	Culture Collection of Fungi	Greece	collaborating party
BCCM-IHEM	Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms - Biomedical fungi and yeasts collection	Belgium	collaborating party
BCCM-LMBP	Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms - Plasmid and DNA Library collection	Belgium	collaborating party
BCCM-LMG	Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms - Bacteria Collection	Belgium	full partner
BCCM-MUCL	Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms - Agro-industrial fungi and yeasts collection	Belgium	collaborating party
CABI	Centre for Agricultural Bioscience International	UK	full partner
CBS	CBS-KNAW Fungal Biodiversity Centre (Centraalbureau voor Schimmelcultures)	The Netherlands	full partner
CCF	Culture Collection of Fungi	Czech Republic	collaborating party
CCIM-IAFB	Culture Collection Of Industrial Microorganisms	Poland	full partner
CCUG	Culture Collection University of Gothenburg	Sweden	full partner
CCY	Culture Collection of Yeasts	Slovakia	collaborating party
CECT	Spanish Type Culture Collection	Spain	full partner
CIP-CRBIP	Biological Resources Center of Pasteur Institute	France	full partner
CIRM-BIA	Centre International de Ressources Microbiennes - Bactéries d'Intérêts Alimentaires	France	full partner
CIRM-BP	International Centre of Microbial Ressources - Pathogenic Bacteria	France	full partner
CIRM-CF	Centre International de Ressources Microbiennes Champignons Filamenteux	France	full partner
CIRM-CFBP	French Collection for Plant-associated Bacteria	France	full partner
CIRM-Levures	Centre International de Ressources Microbiennes - Levures	France	full partner
DBVPG	DBVPG Industrial Yeasts Collection	Italy	collaborating party
DSMZ	Leibniz-Institut DSMZ Deutsche Sammlung für Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen GmbH	Germany	full partner
ICLC	Interlab Cell Line Collection	Italy	full partner
IEGM	Regional Specialized Collection of Alkanotrophic Microorganisms	Russian Federation	collaborating party
ITEM	Agri-Food Toxigenic Fungi Culture Collection	Italy	collaborating party

Culture Collection Acronym	Full name	Country	MIRRI status
MSCL	Microbial Strain Collection of Latvia	Latvia	collaborating party
MUM	Micoteca da Universidade do Minho	Portugal	full partner
MUT	Mycotheca Universitatis Taurinensis	Italy	full partner
NCAIM	National Collection of Agricultural and Industrial Microorganisms	Hungary	collaborating party
NCIMB	National Collection of Industrial Food and Marine Bacteria	UK	collaborating party
PCM	Polish Collection of Microorganisms	Poland	collaborating party
PYCC	Portuguese Yeast Culture Collection	Portugal	collaborating party
SAG	Culture Collection of Algae at Göttingen University	Germany	collaborating party
VKM	All-Russian Collection of Microorganisms	Russian Federation	full partner
VTCC	Technical Research Centre of Finland Culture Collection	Finland	collaborating party

5.4. Annex 4: Overview answers Q10 “Other information types that are very useful for your work”

antibiotic resistance profile
Link to standardised methods that mention its use
Genomic and Proteomic studies and search
application of microorganism
proteome and biosynthetic pathways, phylogenetic trees
citation of ISO and/or CEN standards for growth (incl. culture media etc)
strain informations and their synonyms/ relationships - mostly included and documented for reference material, but most times only restricted to mBRC numbers
available validated DNA primers & probes and specific antibodies
Acces to strains
activity of anti-microbial compounds against specific species
Mating types (where applicable)
MLST scheme if available
susceptibility testing data
temperature resistance
secondary metabolite production
commercialization agreements with depositors should be facilitated by the collection holder
predictive microbiology studies/resources
Existing plasmids and antibodies for the organisms
Metagenomic data
Locality and availability of type specimens
If the current collection is infective
quality assurance; laboratory standards
Identification methods and protocols
Number of copies of a gene of interest, i.e., an antimicrobial resistance gene
ITS restriction pattern
colonisation or infection, animal species
human source and related epidemiology (outbreak strains)
antibiotherapy
If in culture, freeze-dried or extracted DNA/RNA
macroscopic and microscopic aspects
the origin (source) of the "new isolates"
CBD/ABS information/status connected to the strain
METHODS OF DETECTION
Usefulness for any possible applications listed clearly
For industrial application, all the above is important, but it may be questionable whether all that information needs to be provided through mBRCs.
availability of mutant libraries
protein data
the type of preservation
Are there any plans to extend this beyond Europe to include JCM and ATCC for example
about type of sequencing, assembly, bioinformatics
Clinical data, e.g. pathogenicity, isolation sites, patient info, e.g. symptoms,...
a toolbox of available cloned genes
Antimicrobial resistance and gentypes
origin of the strain (sampling place, year, etc.)

growth factors, known inhibitors
database with Reference molecular Methods for detection of GMO, pathogens, meat species
source: for instance, animal, human, etc.

5.5. Annex 5: Overview answers Q11 “List existing databases that are very useful for your work, and to which MIRRI could establish a direct link.”

RAW DATA	CURATED DATA
GenBank, http://www.straininfo.net/ , DSMZ	GenBank, straininfo, DSMZ
DSMZ	DSMZ
Q-bank, LMG, NCPPB, CFBP	Q-bank, LMG, NCPPB, CFBP
SILVA, greengenes	SILVA, greengenes
wdcm straininfo	Wdcm, straininfo
calidad@laboratorioalazor.com	
https://www.dsmz.de , http://www.atcc.org	DSMZ, ATCC
http://www.bacterio.cict.fr/b/brevibacterium.html	LPSN
Medline	PubMed
DSMZ, ATCC	DSMZ, ATCC
NCBI, straininfo	NCBI, straininfo
DSM	DSM
NCBI	NCBI
CABI	CABI
CECT, ATTC, Genbank, Scopus, Sciencedirect, Elsevier, ncbi,	CECT, ATTC, Genbank, Scopus, Sciencedirect, Elsevier, ncbi,
https://www.dsmz.de/	DSMZ
NCBI, EBI, PAMDB (http://genome.ppws.vt.edu/cgi-bin/MLST/home.pl), Regnum Prokaryotae (http://www.tgw1916.net/tests.html), LPSN (http://www.bacterio.net/index.html)	NCBI, EBI, PAMDB, Regnum Prokaryotae, LPSN
Mycotheca Universitatis Taurinensis	MUT
http://www.uv.es/fatwirepub/Satellite/coleccion-espanola-cultivos-tipo/en/coleccion-espanola-cultivos-tipo-1285872233521.html	CECT
www.sciencedirect.com	sciencedirect
NCBI, SILVA, GreenGenes, StrainInfo, RDP	NCBI, SILVA, GreenGenes, StrainInfo, RDP
GenBank, EMBL JGI	GenBank, EMBL JGI
DSMZ, NCTC	DSMZ, NCTC
WDCM , DSMZ, CIP, ATCC	WDCM , DSMZ, CIP, ATCC
CECT, ATCC, DSMZ, MASARYK UNIVERSITY	CECT, ATCC, DSMZ, MASARYK UNIVERSITY
NCBI, CBS, ATCC, CAB-CMI,ETH, VTT,KCL,CTP	NCBI, CBS, ATCC, CABI-CMI,ETH, VTT,KCL,CTP
Genomesonline	GOLD
ATCC, DSM, LMG	ATCC, DSMZ, LMG
DSMZ; Greengenes	DSMZ; Greengenes
DSMZ, NCIMB, ATCC, BCCM	DSMZ, NCIMB, ATCC, BCCM
http://www.microbial-ecology.net/probebase/	Probebase
DSMZ, CECT, ATCC	DSMZ, CECT, ATCC
ATCC, DSMZ, CIP, GenBank	ATCC, DSMZ, CIP, GenBank
www.dsmz.de	DSMZ
LPSN	LPSN
gene bank	genebank
CBS, DSMZ,ATCC, VKM	CBS, DSMZ,ATCC, VKM
European collections like DSMZ, CECT, CCUG, Straininfo, Index Fungorum, Mycobank,etc	DSMZ, CECT, CCUG, Straininfo, Index Fungorum, Mycobank
ncbi, BCCM/LMG	ncbi, BCCM LMG
strain.info	straininfo

STCC, DSMZ, ATCC	STCC, DSMZ, ATCC
CECT, ATCC, DSM	CECT, ATCC, DSMZ
NCBI	NCBI
http://ec.europa.eu/food/food/rapidalert/index_en.htm	RASFF
Euroscarf	Euroscarf
Helicobacter group Database	Helicobacter group Database
CECT, DSMZ	CECT, DSMZ
SRA, GEO	SRA, GEO
genbank	genbank
catalogue information	
DSMZ; ATCC	DSMZ; ATCC
DSMZ ATCC	DSMZ ATCC
dsmz, atcc, cls, ECACC, HSRRB, ncbi,	dsmz, atcc, cls, ECACC, HSRRB, ncbi,
yeastgenome.org	SGD
NCBI, GenBank, SILVA, ProbeCheck	NCBI, GenBank, SILVA, ProbeCheck
links for genomes and proteomes, such as JGI and NCBI	JGI NCBI
http://www.indexfungorum.org/names/names.asp ; http://www.mycobank.org/ ; http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/	Indexfungorum, mycobank, PubMed
CCUG, NCBI, DSM, ATCC, JCM	CCUG, NCBI, DSMZ, ATCC, JCM
DSMZ, CCUG, LMG	DSMZ, CCUG, LMG
DSMZ, CCUG	DSMZ, CCUG
DSMZ, CCUG, NTC	DSMZ, CCUG, NTC
Ribosomal Database Project	RDP
StrainInfo	StrainInfo
ncbi	ncbi
Pubmed, Web of knowledge	Pubmed, Web of knowledge
GenBank; PubMed	GenBank; PubMed
NCBI RDP HOMD	NCBI RDP HOMD
genbank, dsmz, atcc	genbank, dsmz, atcc
Uniprot, Pfam	Uniprot, Pfam
dsmz, atcc	dsmz, atcc
ncbi, dsmz, dpvweb	ncbi, dsmz, dpvweb
NCBI, EZtaxon	NCBI, EZtaxon
GCM	GCM
MBGD	MBGD
GenBank	GenBank
NCBI, StrainInfo	NCBI, StrainInfo
GenBank	GenBank
NCBI, SwissProt	NCBI, SwissProt
CCY Slovakia	CCY
kegs, ncbi, ebi	kegg, ncbi, ebi
DSMZ	DSMZ
probase; DMSZ	probase; DMSZ
BRENDA, KEGG, BLAST	BRENDA, KEGG, BLAST
http://www.dsmz.de/ ; http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/ ; http://toxgen.labkm.net/toxgen/intro/ ; http://biograph.be/ ; http://www.genome.jp/kegg/kegg2.html ; http://www.ezbiocloud.net/	DSMZ, PubMed, TOXGEN? , BioGraph, KEGG, ezbiocloud
AIDS reagents program	AIDS reagents program
CABI, CBS, DSMZ	CABI, CBS, DSMZ
GenBank, StrainInfo	GenBank, StrainInfo
where specific strains can be purchased	where specific strains can be purchased

http://www.straininfo.net/	http://www.straininfo.net/
PubMed	PubMed
ncbi	ncbi
CECT; ATCC; NCTC	CECT; ATCC; NCTC
Strain info	Strain info
NCBI	NCBI
ATCC	ATCC
DSMZ, NRRL, ATCC	DSMZ, NRRL, ATCC
cect	cect
ncbi pubmed, string (EMBL)	ncbi pubmed, string (EMBL)
DSMZ, BCCM/LMG	DSMZ, BCCM/LMG
www.straininfo.net	www.straininfo.net
straininfo; NCBI Genbank BLAST	straininfo; NCBI Genbank BLAST
NCBI	NCBI
pubmed	pubmed
DSMZ, LMG	DSMZ, LMG
NCBI, GREENGENES, PROBEASE	NCBI, GREENGENES, PROBEASE
Ribosome Database Project	Ribosome Database Project
NCBI, TGD	NCBI, TGD
GenBank, Bacterial Nomenclature	GenBank, Bacterial Nomenclature
http://isolate.fusariumdb.org ; http://www.mycologylab.org/DefaultInfo.aspx?Page=ITSCContributors ; http://mlst.mycologylab.org ; http://nt.ars-grin.gov/fungalatabases ; http://www.fungalbarcoding.org/BioMICS.aspx ; http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/refseq	http://isolate.fusariumdb.org ; http://www.mycologylab.org/DefaultInfo.aspx?Page=ITSCContributors ; http://mlst.mycologylab.org ; http://nt.ars-grin.gov/fungalatabases ; http://www.fungalbarcoding.org/BioMICS.aspx ; http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/refseq
NCBI, ATCC (because is in America)	NCBI, ATCC (because is in America)
GenBank	GenBank
DSMZ, EMBL	DSMZ, EMBL
DSMZ, NCBI	DSMZ, NCBI
Blast	Blast
BIOLOMICS CBS Utrecht, FUSARIUM ID, USDA (Agriculture), ITS Fungal Database University of Sydney, GenBank	BIOLOMICS CBS Utrecht, FUSARIUM ID, USDA (Agriculture), ITS Fungal Database University of Sydney, GenBank
GenBank	GenBank
AddGene, ATCC, Coriell	AddGene, ATCC, Coriell
ATCC	ATCC
NCBI Genbank	NCBI Genbank
http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/ , http://www.straininfo.net/	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/ , http://www.straininfo.net/
GenBank	GenBank
DSMZ, CCM, ATCC	DSMZ, CCM, ATCC
www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov	www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov
Leibniz Institute DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures, National Collection of Type Cultures, Spanish Type Culture Collection	Leibniz Institute DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures, National Collection of Type Cultures, National Collection of Type Cultures, Spanish Type Culture Collection
NRRL	NRRL
NCBI, ATCC, DSMZ, CCM	NCBI, ATCC, DSMZ, CCM
NRRL (USA),	NRRL (USA),

NCBI	NCBI
BCCM	BCCM
brenda,	brenda,
dszm.de	dszm.de
CCY; CBS; NRRL	CCY; CBS; NRRL
DSMZ and LMG	DSMZ and LMG
rdp	rdp
the research about the microbial related diseases	the research about the microbial related diseases
taxonomy and classification	taxonomy and classification
bacterio.net	bacterio.net
CECT, NCPF, CBS, ATCC	CECT, NCPF, CBS, ATCC
ncbi	ncbi
CECT, ATCC	CECT, ATCC
Now we use only informations present on the web	Now we use only informations present on the web
Science direct	Science direct
CECT	CECT
Scopus, FASTA, ExPaSy, PubMed, WOK	Scopus, FASTA, ExPaSy, PubMed, WOK
BRENDA enzyme database	BRENDA enzyme database
NCBI DBs, Plant Viruses Online	NCBI DBs, Plant Viruses Online
DSMZ, ATCC, ARS culture collection, BCCM, IFO, NBRC, NCIMB, CCOS	DSMZ, ATCC, ARS culture collection, BCCM, IFO, NBRC, NCIMB, CCOS
NCTC, CECT, ATCC	NCTC, CECT, ATCC
Culture Collection of Switzerland (CCOS)	Culture Collection of Switzerland (CCOS)
ATCC	ATCC
e.g. EzTaxon, GenBank, CARD, ARDB	e.g. EzTaxon, GenBank, CARD, ARDB
DSMZ, ATCC, NCBI, Pubmed	DSMZ, ATCC, NCBI, Pubmed
genbank, RDP	genbank, RDP
LPSN, NCBI	LPSN, NCBI
NCBI, DSMZ, ATCC, CECT, RRnDB, ARB, SILVA, CAMERA	NCBI, DSMZ, ATCC, CECT, RRnDB, ARB, SILVA, CAMERA
CECT, ATCC	CECT, ATCC
DSMZ, Germany	DSMZ, Germany
CECT, NCBI	CECT, NCBI
CECT, DSMZ, ATCC, BCCM/LMG, NCIMB	CECT, DSMZ, ATCC, BCCM/LMG, NCIMB
CECT, CBS	CECT, CBS
Midi Inc.	Midi Inc.
CECT. ALLERGEN.ORG	CECT. ALLERGEN.ORG
NCBI	NCBI
CBS database	CBS database
R UE 2073/2005	R UE 2073/2005
Colección Española de Cultivos Tipo "www.cect.org/"	Colección Española de Cultivos Tipo "www.cect.org/"
EMBL, BLAST, Genbank	EMBL, BLAST, Genbank
GenBank, Uniprot, CECT, DSMZ, Enzyme Comission	GenBank, Uniprot, CECT, DSMZ, Enzyme Comission
genome databases	genome databases
http://www.straininfo.net/	http://www.straininfo.net/
NCBI, ATCC, CECT, NCTC	NCBI, ATCC, CECT, NCTC
NCBI	NCBI

ATCC, NCTC, CECT, University of Gotteborg	ATCC, NCTC, CECT, University of Gotteborg
cect	cect
CECT, DSMZ, CIP, BCCM, NCYC, NCIMB	CECT, DSMZ, CIP, BCCM, NCYC, NCIMB
NCBI	NCBI
ARB, RDP, Greengenes	ARB, RDP, Greengenes
www.microbiologyinpictures.com;www.microbelibrary.org/; sciencedirect	www.microbiologyinpictures.com;www.microbelibrary.org/; sciencedirect
NCBI (PubMed, BLAST)	NCBI (PubMed, BLAST)
CECT, BCCM, CBS, CABI, NCBI	CECT, BCCM, CBS, CABI, NCBI
AESAN, HPA,CECT	AESAN, HPA,CECT
CECT	CECT
CECT	CECT
CECT	CECT
http://www.uv.es/cect; http://ncppb.fera.defra.gov.uk/; ivia.es; http://www.lgcstandards-atcc.org/?geo_country=es; https://www.dsmz.de/;	http://www.uv.es/cect; http://ncppb.fera.defra.gov.uk/; ivia.es; http://www.lgcstandards-atcc.org/?geo_country=es; https://www.dsmz.de/;
Ez taxon, Antismash, NCBI	Ez taxon, Antismash, NCBI
http://www.lgcstandards-atcc.org/	http://www.lgcstandards-atcc.org/
Allergome; IUIS Allergen; SDAP - Structural Database of Allergenic Proteins; UniProtKB	Allergome; IUIS Allergen; SDAP - Structural Database of Allergenic Proteins; UniProtKB
CECT	CECT
ARM	ARM
Colección Española de cultivos tipo	Colección Española de cultivos tipo
GROWTH CONDITIONS AND REQUIREMENTS	GROWTH CONDITIONS AND REQUIREMENTS
CECT, ATCC, DSMZ	CECT, ATCC, DSMZ
CDC, NCBIMB	CDC, NCBIMB
cect, combase	cect, combase
SprectaBank	SprectaBank
pubmed, candida DB, JGI fungi portal	pubmed, candida DB, JGI fungi portal
atcc	atcc
ncbi	ncbi
PubMed-NCBI	PubMed-NCBI
wok	wok
Ribosomal Database Project	Ribosomal Database Project
GenBank, Q-Bank, EPPO	GenBank, Q-Bank, EPPO
CBS/Mycobank, DSMz, ATCC	CBS/Mycobank, DSMz, ATCC
Q-bank, NCBI, Phytophthora Database	Q-bank, NCBI, Phytophthora Database
GenBank data base	GenBank data base
BCCM	BCCM
Sanger institute, http://cellfinder.org, http://clkb.ncibi.org,	Sanger institute, http://cellfinder.org, http://clkb.ncibi.org,
NCBI, Swiss PROT	NCBI, Swiss PROT
http://www.naktuinbouw.nl/sites/naktuinbouw.eu/files/Isolatenlijst%20website%202012.pdf	http://www.naktuinbouw.nl/sites/naktuinbouw.eu/files/Isolatenlijst%20website%202012.pdf
SILVA database	SILVA database
vibroscope	vibroscope
CBS LMG BCCM DSZM	CBS LMG BCCM DSZM

Straininfo database, NCBI, Integrated Microbial Genomes	Straininfo database, NCBI, Integrated Microbial Genomes
EMBL	EMBL
http://www.i-beg.eu/ ; http://invam.wvu.edu/ ; http://www.indexfungorum.org/Names/Names.asp	http://www.i-beg.eu/ ; http://invam.wvu.edu/ ; http://www.indexfungorum.org/Names/Names.asp
PAhytophthora Database, World Phytophthora Genetic Resource Collection	PAhytophthora Database, World Phytophthora Genetic Resource Collection
MTCC, India and any fungal database	MTCC, India and any fungal database
GENBANK, MYCOBANK	GENBANK, MYCOBANK
NCBI, EBI, RDP, LTP, MLST,	NCBI, EBI, RDP, LTP, MLST,
BCCM - BCCM/MUCL (Agro)Industrial Fungi & Yeasts Collection	BCCM - BCCM/MUCL (Agro)Industrial Fungi & Yeasts Collection
CLSI, EUCAST, NCBI, Ribosomal Database Project, ExTaxon, LPSN	CLSI, EUCAST, NCBI, Ribosomal Database Project, ExTaxon, LPSN
genbank, pubmed, isi web of Knowledge, JCR	genbank, pubmed, isi web of Knowledge, JCR
ncbi	ncbi
CECT, DSMZ, ATCC, BCCM, CCUG	CECT, DSMZ, ATCC, BCCM, CCUG
http://www.wfcc.info/ ; http://www.cabri.org/collections.html	http://www.wfcc.info/ ; http://www.cabri.org/collections.html
NCBI, IMG microbial genome, BIOcyc,	NCBI, IMG microbial genome, BIOcyc,
CBS, ATCC, UAMH, IMI	CBS, ATCC, UAMH, IMI
French collection of plant pathogenic bacteria	French collection of plant pathogenic bacteria
BCCM, ATCC, CCAP	BCCM, ATCC, CCAP
CECT	CECT
CFBP, NCPPB, CIP, PSS, DGBBC	CFBP, NCPPB, CIP, PSS, DGBBC
catalogueoflife.org	catalogueoflife.org
Combase.com, PMP.com	Combase.com, PMP.com
BCCM-LMG, DSMZ, CNCM, NCIMB	BCCM-LMG, DSMZ, CNCM, NCIMB
addgene	addgene
CECT	CECT
SubtiList	SubtiList
pubmed	pubmed
ATCC; bacmap; EBI; NCBI; db of each single microbe genome project;JCVI	ATCC; bacmap; EBI; NCBI; db of each single microbe genome project;JCVI
CECT Collection	CECT Collection
CECT	CECT
catalogues of different culture collections	catalogues of different culture collections
Probe base	Probe base
CECT	CECT
Index Fungorum; CBS data base	Index Fungorum; CBS data base
http://www.uv.es/cect	http://www.uv.es/cect
dsmz, cect	dsmz, cect
CECT, ATCC	CECT, ATCC
Bacillus Genetic Sotck Center	Bacillus Genetic Sotck Center
CECT	CECT
ATCC, CECT, NCTC	ATCC, CECT, NCTC
psoler@aguasdevalencia.es	psoler@aguasdevalencia.es
CECT, genbank, ATCC	CECT, genbank, ATCC

Taxonomy and classification	Taxonomy and classification
Genbank	Genbank
CECT	CECT
DMSZ, CECT	DMSZ, CECT
CECT, ATCC, NCTC, Institute Pasteur database, DSMZ	CECT, ATCC, NCTC, Institute Pasteur database, DSMZ
apiweb	apiweb
CBS, DSMZ	CBS, DSMZ
Colección española de cultivos tipo	Colección española de cultivos tipo
CECT	CECT
LGC, IELAB	LGC, IELAB
cect	cect
CECT	CECT
CECT, ATCC, NCBI, EMBL	CECT, ATCC, NCBI, EMBL
cect	cect
ATCC	ATCC
NCBI-PubMed; Espacenet	NCBI-PubMed; Espacenet
NCBI, LPSN, The Ribosomal Database Project, mycobank, ictvonline, straininfo.net	NCBI, LPSN, The Ribosomal Database Project, mycobank, ictvonline, straininfo.net
cbs	cbs
ATCC, MTCC	ATCC, MTCC
DSMZ, LGC, CBS	DSMZ, LGC, CBS
ATCC, UBC, CBS, NRRL, IMI	ATCC, UBC, CBS, NRRL, IMI
CECT; Strain Info	CECT; Strain Info
KEGG	KEGG
NCBI, PROBEASE	NCBI, PROBEASE
MBGD; IMG;	MBGD; IMG;
CECT, CBS,	CECT, CBS,
we have our own in-house database and also use microbial NP databases such as AntiBase	we have our own in-house database and also use microbial NP databases such as AntiBase
CCUG, DSMZ, CCT	CCUG, DSMZ, CCT
bacterio-net; straininfo.net; ezbiocloud.net; arb-silva.. living tree; NCBI; img.jgi.doe.gov; genomesonline.org	bacterio-net; straininfo.net; ezbiocloud.net; arb-silva.. living tree; NCBI; img.jgi.doe.gov; genomesonline.org
pubmed, genbank	pubmed, genbank
science direct	science direct
DSMZ, CECT, LMG	DSMZ, CECT, LMG
culture type collections, NCBI, web of knowlegment,...	culture type collections, NCBI, web of knowlegment,...
NCBI, JGI, ATCC, DSMZ, LGM, CECT	NCBI, JGI, ATCC, DSMZ, LGM, CECT
CCUG, StrainInfo	CCUG, StrainInfo
CECT NTCC ATCC	CECT NTCC ATCC
http://www.bacterio.net/	http://www.bacterio.net/
ATCC Sci-Fi	ATCC Sci-Fi
CCY Bratislava	CCY Bratislava
DSMZ; ATCC; PYCC; NRRL; CECT	DSMZ; ATCC; PYCC; NRRL; CECT
NCBI	NCBI
CCY Slovakia, http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi	CCY Slovakia, http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi

straininfo, LPSN, NCBI, Etaxon, catalogues of individual culture collections	straininfo, LPSN, NCBI, Etaxon, catalogues of individual culture collections
http://www.vkm.ru/	http://www.vkm.ru/
dsmz	dsmz
ATCC, Genbank	ATCC, Genbank
ATCC, DMSZ	ATCC, DMSZ
http://www.dsmz.de/catalogues/catalogue-microorganisms.html	http://www.dsmz.de/catalogues/catalogue-microorganisms.html
DSMZ, culture collection of Switzerland	DSMZ, culture collection of Switzerland
NCAIM Hungary, CCAP SAMS Dcotland	NCAIM Hungary, CCAP SAMS Dcotland
http://www.dsmz.de/ ; http://www.cbs.knaw.nl/	http://www.dsmz.de/ ; http://www.cbs.knaw.nl/
NCBI	NCBI
NCBI, DSMZ	NCBI, DSMZ
ATCC, NCTC, CECT, DSM	ATCC, NCTC, CECT, DSM
MLST databases; The collection of bacteria, Institute Pasteur; Leptospira Library (Royal Tropical Institute - KIT, Amsterdam)	MLST databases; The collection of bacteria, Institute Pasteur; Leptospira Library (Royal Tropical Institute - KIT, Amsterdam)
ATCC collection	ATCC collection
ATCC, DSMZ, LMG	ATCC, DSMZ, LMG
Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes; BRENDA	Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes; BRENDA
Euzeby; EZbiocloud	Euzeby; EZbiocloud
DSMZ, BGSC, ATCC	DSMZ, BGSC, ATCC
CAZY	CAZY
genbank, pubmed	genbank, pubmed
ATCC, DSMZ	ATCC, DSMZ
ATCC, DSMZ	ATCC, DSMZ
BLAST; StreptoBASE; streptomyces.org.uk ; GeneDB	BLAST; StreptoBASE; streptomyces.org.uk ; GeneDB
NCBI	NCBI
GENBANK	GENBANK
DSMZ; CCUG; CIP	DSMZ; CCUG; CIP
PubMed	PubMed
NCBI/EMBL/DBJ; List of Prokaryote names with Standing in Nomenclature	NCBI/EMBL/DBJ; List of Prokaryote names with Standing in Nomenclature
full genome sequence	full genome sequence
pubmed	pubmed
Q-BANK NEMATODES	Q-BANK NEMATODES
DSMZ, Euzeby	DSMZ, Euzeby
NCBI databases, AllergenOnline database (to get a link to potential allergenicity issues)	NCBI databases, AllergenOnline database (to get a link to potential allergenicity issues)
taxonomy and classification	taxonomy and classification
LPSN (bacterio.net)	LPSN (bacterio.net)
dsmz	dsmz
ncbi	ncbi
SILVA	SILVA
GenBank	GenBank
DSMZ & ATCC	DSMZ & ATCC
ATCC CCUG LMG FSC	ATCC CCUG LMG FSC

NCBI pubmed, microbial genomes	NCBI pubmed, microbial genomes
UNITE, EZTaxon	UNITE, EZTaxon
AmericanTypeCultureCollection	AmericanTypeCultureCollection
DSMZ, LMG, CCUG	DSMZ, LMG, CCUG
http://www.bacterio.net/	http://www.bacterio.net/
CCUG, NCBI, Greengenes, Ridom, RDP	CCUG, NCBI, Greengenes, Ridom, RDP
DSMZ	DSMZ
JSpecies, List of Prokaryotic Names with Standing in Nomenclature	JSpecies, List of Prokaryotic Names with Standing in Nomenclature
DSM. NCTC	DSM. NCTC
culture collections websites; List of Bacterial Names; GenBank	culture collections websites; List of Bacterial Names; GenBank
PDB Uniprot	PDB Uniprot
BLAST	BLAST
web of knowledge, pub-med	web of knowledge, pub-med
Enzyme database Brenda; http://www.brenda-enzymes.org	Enzyme database Brenda; http://www.brenda-enzymes.org
http://www.sccap.dk/	http://www.sccap.dk/
DSMZ, NCBI, ATCC	DSMZ, NCBI, ATCC
ATCC DSMZ	ATCC DSMZ
strain passport, Euzeby list of Approved Names, NCBI	strain passport, Euzeby list of Approved Names, NCBI
biocyc, brenda, patric, genbank	biocyc, brenda, patric, genbank
IMG, RAST, NCBI	IMG, RAST, NCBI
DSMZ, ATCC, NCBI DNA and protein sequence	DSMZ, ATCC, NCBI DNA and protein sequence
www.atcc.org	www.atcc.org
ATCC DSMZ	ATCC DSMZ
NCBI, KEGG genome	NCBI, KEGG genome
DSMZ, ATCC, SAG	DSMZ, ATCC, SAG
DSMZ, LPSN, NCBI	DSMZ, LPSN, NCBI
http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/ , http://www.mycobank.org/	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/ , http://www.mycobank.org/
DSMZ, EMBL	DSMZ, EMBL
DSMZ	DSMZ
IMG especially, NCBI, PSIPRED	IMG especially, NCBI, PSIPRED
NCBI, IMG	NCBI, IMG
NCBI	NCBI
CBS Culture collection, American type culture collection	CBS Culture collection, American type culture collection
Saccharomyes genome database (SGD), NCBI	Saccharomyes genome database (SGD), NCBI
List of Prokaryotic Names with Standing in Nomenclature (http://www.bacterio.net/)	List of Prokaryotic Names with Standing in Nomenclature (http://www.bacterio.net/)
NCTC, ATCC, DMZ, NARSA, BEI	NCTC, ATCC, DMZ, NARSA, BEI
ATCC, DSMZ	ATCC, DSMZ
DSMZ, CCUG, NCTC	DSMZ, CCUG, NCTC
http://www.straininfo.net/	http://www.straininfo.net/
DSMZ, HPA, ATCC, BLAST, Bacterionet	DSMZ, HPA, ATCC, BLAST, Bacterionet
CECT, DSMZ, NCIMB, ACOI	CECT, DSMZ, NCIMB, ACOI
Blast, Pubmed	Blast, Pubmed
DZSM	DZSM
PubMed, SAG	PubMed, SAG

DSMZ (my favourite one), NCIMB, ATCC	DSMZ (my favourite one), NCIMB, ATCC
NCBI, Ez-taxon	NCBI, Ez-taxon
sgd	sgd
KEGG	KEGG
Uniprot, PDB, NCBI	Uniprot, PDB, NCBI
none that i know of	none that i know of
sequence DB (EMBL, HDP.....), mBRCs all over the world,	sequence DB (EMBL, HDP.....), mBRCs all over the world,
NCBI, EzTaxon,	NCBI, EzTaxon,
PubMed, Expasy, UniProt,	PubMed, Expasy, UniProt,
NCBI, Pfam, SILVA, GrennGenes, RDP	NCBI, Pfam, SILVA, GrennGenes, RDP
NCBI and DSMZ	NCBI and DSMZ
RDP, Green genes, Silva	RDP, Green genes, Silva
CDC, ATCC, DSMZ	CDC, ATCC, DSMZ
Pubmed, GoldGenomes	Pubmed, GoldGenomes
NCBI databases, straininfo.net, KEGG, Pathogen Safety Data Sheets and Risk Assessment, http://www.disinfectiondatabase.com/	NCBI databases, straininfo.net, KEGG, Pathogen Safety Data Sheets and Risk Assessment, http://www.disinfectiondatabase.com/
dsmz, atcc, barcode life, gmo detection method database, EU Database of Reference Methods for GMO Analysis	dsmz, atcc, barcode life, gmo detection method database, EU Database of Reference Methods for GMO Analysis
EBI, NCBI	EBI, NCBI
DSMZ - Germany; ATCC - USA; GenBank (National Center for Biotechnology Information)	DSMZ - Germany; ATCC - USA; GenBank (National Center for Biotechnology Information)
Pubmed, Euzaby	Pubmed, Euzaby
DSMZ, ATCC	DSMZ, ATCC
PubMed, Scopus	PubMed, Scopus

5.6. Annex 6: Overview answers Q19 “Other formats relevant for your work”

lyophilized standard strains
genomic DNAs of strains, frozen cell pellets in microtiterplates
For us it is enough to receive an axenic culture in whatever format that is easy to resurrect, and with a minimum CFU count (no need to know how many bacteria are there)
Single culture in water or in merdes oil, steril conditions
DNA
lyophilised material
genomic DNA
Mixed culture with a specific functional/ecological role
DNA / RNA preparations // or inactivated cellular material
DNA
dna
DNA & RNA from precited propositions
purified liquid medium culture
DNA
good preservation conditions easy to mail by post
On-line, secure, curated and interactive database (members full access, customers limited access) of microscopic features of purchased microorganism
liophilized for long trips
dry stock that can be shipped without dry or wet ice
lyophilized strain
Faeces samples mixed from several donors and checked for major human pathogens
Cultures (mixed or pure) with known properties (gene, transcripts, or phenotype)
DNA extract
DNA from known organisms with known concentration
active culture
lyophilic
lyophilized
Plant specifically infected matherial, insect vectors,
Reference material for genomic uses (standards for PCR...)
single strain provided in microtiter plates for easy/low contamination risk for multiple uses
Pure cultures of well-documented origin
plate culture
culture in different matrices
gDNA
Small petri dish instead of culture tubes
lyophilized format
Freeze-dried or in form of extracted DNA/RNA
small plates; stabs
plasmids, genomic DNA
DNA
plate with colony? DNA
Live cultures (i.e. not e.g. freeze-dried)
genomic DNA
DNA
As long as culture is healthy, CFU information is not needed
DNA extracts

how about several "doses" in eppendorf tubes or seringes for direct inoculation ?
DNA
Genomic extracts of known microorganisms
Large scale inoculum would be great for animal cell lines

5.7. Annex 7: Overview answers Q22 “List the top three of microorganism groups important for your work but at present not offered by public mBRCs.”

1	2	3
Bifidobacterium	Lactobacillus	Streptococcus
Archae	Fungi	Protozoa
Xylella fastidiosa (very restricted by public mBRCs)	Erwinia pyrifoliae (very restricted by public mBRCs)	Different Pseudomonas sp.
Lactobacillae	Streptococcus	Lactococcus
Bacteria with specific mutations	Bacteria with specific reporter genes	Plasmids for various molecular work
Trichoderma spp	Bacillus spp	
Legionella	E. coli	Staphilocococcus aureus
pLANT VIRUSES THAT ARE NOT MECHANICALLY TRANSMISSIBLE		
bacillus	actinomycetes	gluconobacter
streptomyces sp	bacillus sp	E. coli
Mycobacterium	Actinomycetes	Arthrobacter, Brevibacter
vibrios with toxin genes	water organisms	
silicate-dissolving bacteria	rock phosphate-solubilizing fungus	poly-(γ-glutamic acid) -producing microorganisms
metagenomic libraries/gDNAs of environmental samples	non-culturables..	
Plasmodium falciparum		
"Candidatus Liberibacter" species		
Actinomycetes	Yeasts	lipase producing microorganisms
viruses		
fungus specific sequences	transformed fungi	
bacteria	archaea	
Streptococcus pneumoniae various serotypes		
Vibrio vulnificus	Photobacterium damsela subsp. damsela	Photobacterium damsela subsp. piscicida
unculturable microorganisms		
Iron oxidisers	archaeal ammonia oxidisers	
PAO	AOB	NOB
Cupriavidus necator	Sporobolomyces spp.	Streptococcus zooepidemicus
Herpesviruses		
actinobacteria	firmicutes	proteobacteria
archaea	fungi	algae
Fungi		
vibro cholera for vaccine production	bordetella pertusis for vaccine production	clostridium tetani for vaccine production
Campylobacter jejuni /coli/lari	norovirus GI /GII	Virus hepatitis A
norovirus		
Sebacinaceae		
Helicobacter		
Propionibacteria	Malassezia	Trichophyton
Leptospira		
E.coli	P.mirabilis	M.smegmatis
special tumor cell lines		
agrobacterium (some already exist)	algae (green, red, diatoms)	cyanobacteria (some already exist)

Dehalococcoides mccartyi	Dehalogenimonas lykanthroporepellens	
Some Actinomycetes, Streptomycetes	Some Basidiomycetes	Some Zygomycetes
MTCC, Imtech, Chandigarh, India		
stapilococcus	pseudomonas	enterococcus
archaea		
plant viruses	viroids	phytoplasma
Risk Group II		
Staphylococcus epidermidis	Staphylococcus aureus	Gardenerella vaginalis
Saccharomyces cerevisiae		
Lactic acid bacteria	Foodborne pathogens	
ammonia oxidizing archaea		
Gram - bacteria (Pseudomonas, Escherichia)	Gram + bacterie (Staphylocoques, streptocoques)	Yeasts and moulds (Candida, Aspergillus)
anaerobic fungi	some anaerobic bacterial strains	
viruses		
Most are covered but is more the quality of the organism that matters in p[articular it is useful to have recently isolated organisms even of those belonging to well known and documented groups		
BSL3 bacteria		
Methanogenic archaea	Pyrococcus sp.	Sulfate reducing microorganisms
Lyshmania		
are available which need		
Nanjing agricultural University, resource and environmental college microbe collection centre	beijing microbial collection centre	
Halophilic archaeae (few available)		
E. coli	beyond only eukaryotic cells actually	
lignocellulose degrading fungi	anaerobic/microaerobic bacteria	special Clostridia, and Actinomycetes
verotoxin-producing E. coli	toxin-producing Staphylococci	toxin-producing bacillus cereus
Bacteria	Fungi	Algae
lactic acid bacteria	bifidobacteria	Streptomyces
Not this time	Not this time	Not this time
Pleociocistis pacifica	Tetrahymena thermophila	Paramecium tetraurelia
Liberibacter		
Endemic fungi		
chemolitoautotrophs	extremophiles	environmental samples
Gram positive	Pseudomonas group	Enterobacteria
Bacteria	yeast	archaea
escherichia coli k12		
Bacteria	Filamentous fungi	Yeast
phytophthora spp.		
virusses of bulbous flowers	viruses of ornamentals	
bacillus cereus	legionella pneumophila	
methanogenic archea		
(Poly)extremophiles		
oil reservoirs microorganisms		
strains different from the type strain		
micro algae	strains different from type strain	
Deinococcus/thermus	Actinobacteria	Proteobacteria
microbial resources exist	agricultural microorganisms	biotechnology
geobacter	archaea	homoacetogenics
Methanogens	mycorrhiza	
lactobacilli	diphtheria	anthracoids

Raistonia	Sphingomonas	
Candidatus Liberibacter spp.		
Cyanobacteria		
Gluconobacter oxydans	Enterobacter aerogenes	Azotobacter vinilandii
E. coli STEC (O145; O104).		
phytoplasmas		
Harboring specific biodegrading genes	Harboring specific antibiotic resistance genes	
Environmental isolates from water/food		
Mycobacteria	Brucella	Clostridia
Cyanobacteria	Gloeobacter	Ancient Archaeal Group
mesophilic crenarchaeota (e.g. ammonia oxidizing archaea)		
Microalgae (different genera)		
Vine wood phytopathogenic fungi		
candidatus Liberibacter ...		
E coli	Sthaphilococcus aureus	H influenzae
enterobacteriaceae	micrococaceae	streptococaceae
burkholderia cepacia		
known hosts of phages	halophilic bacteriophages	protein-overproducing strains
Some Legionella strains	Helminths (eggs)	Enterovirus
yeasts	fungi	lactic bacteria
Entomopathogenic microorganisms	Antagonistic Microorganisms of Pathogenic Fungi	
environmental bacteria	environmental fungi	environmental microalgae
Bacillus thuringiensis tenebrionis		
plant fastidious microorganism		
environmental strains in cosmetic areas		
Actinobacteria	Firmicutes	Proteobacteria
Campylobacter jejuni	clostridium botulinum	
PEDV		
Postharvest decay fungi	Downy Mildew	Powdery Mildews
Staphylococcus sp.	Streptococcus sp.	Escherichia coli
Campylobacter	Arcobacter	Helicobacter
Escherichia coli	Salmonela	Clostridium perfringens
Some gut bacteria, especially those isolated from the rumen		
microorganisms as plant biotrophs	phytoplasmas?	
Agaricus bisporus var. eurotetrasporus	Agaricus bisporus	
phytoplasmas	insects	nematodes
Streptomycetes	Bacteriophages	Archaea
enterobacteriae		
vegetable pathogenic fungi	vegetable pathogenic bacteria	vegetable pathogenic viruses
Pseudomonas savastanoy nt 105		
Quantifier strain Salmonella enteritidis		
Quantified Salmonella enteritidis		
Actinomicetes		
virus	nematodes	obligate fungi
Anaerobes		
some Phytophthora sp.	obligate plant pathogens such as rusts and powdery mildew	
Glomus macrocarpum	Acaulospora elegans	Dentiscutata reticulata
Phytophthora	Pythium	Phytopythium
Plant pathogenic fungus for research use		

Mycoplasma	Ehrlichia, Borrelia, Anaplasma	Spirochetes, Treponema
Metschnikowia	Candida	Saccharomyces
various Brachyspira species	various Mycoplasma species	
Ralstonia	Pseudomonas	Escherichia
Salmonella spp	L.monocytogenes	E.coli STEC
E. coli		
candidatus liberibacter asiaticus / africanus / americanus		
Lactic acid bacteria	Bacillus	Bifidobacteria
e.coli with deleted genes of specific house keeping proteins		
Staph Enterotoxin		
Escherichia coli	Staphylococcus aureus	Aspergillus niger
Clostridium spores with known D-value	Bacillus subtilis spores with known D-value	
Anammox bacteria		
Microalgae		
Anaerobic bacteria	Some Yeast and fungi	
Antracophyllum discolor		
Chromatium		
extremophiles	anaerobic	unculturable archaea
E.coli	Enterobacter	Clostridium perfringens
wildlife strains		
Plasmopara viticola	Erysiphe necator	
Low level quantified reference material for thermophilic Campylobacter spp (C. jejuni or C. coli)		
Bacteria	Actinomycetes	
strains with certain antimicrobial resistance genes		
s. epidermidis	cupriavidus	
AMF	Nitrificants	P solubilizers
Alternaria tomato strain	Rhizoctonia solani AG-groups	
Saprotrophic fungi	Ectomycorrhizal fungi	
Escherichia coli	Enterococcus faecalis	Pseudomonas aeruginosa
VARIETY OF BREWER'S YEAST STRAINS		
Legionella spp		
recent clinical isolates of human fungal pathogens	recent clinical isolates of human bacterial pathogens	
trichoderma harzianum	pseudomonas fluorescens	fusarium oxysporum
lactic acid bacteria	yeast	
Helicobacter	Legionella	pseudomonas
info not available		
Staphylococcus intermedius		
Enterobacteriaceae	Listeria monocytogenes	Salmonella spp.
anammox	autotrophically nitrifying bacteria	
Bifidobacterium	Lactobacillus	Clostridium
Some Trichoderma strains	Some phytopathogenic fungi	
ectomycorrhizal fungi	mycorrhizal helper bacteria	rhizobacteria
yeast	lactic acid bacteria	spoilage microorganisms
vibrio cholerae	vibrio parahaemolyticus	vibrio vulnificus
lactobacillus plantarum		
anaerobic fungi		
Seeliger's Listeria Collection	Vibrio collections at diverse labs in Europe	Sources for Clostridium botulinum
e.coli	salmonella	listeria
baculovirus		

Bifidobacterium from peculiar sources		
bacteria	yeast	mold
Hyperthermophiles	Microalgae	
plasmodia		
heliobacteria,	gren sulfur bacteria,	obligately anaerobic bacteria in general not available at many mBRCs
herpesviruses	poxxviruses	retroviruses
Plant viruses that cannot be analyzed by ELISA	Many plant pathogenic bacteria/fungi	Phytoplasmas
Algae, there is no in Hungary		
Lactic acid bacteria	mould: Penicillium, Aspergillus, Fusarium	Enterobacteriaceae
Borrelia burgdorderi s.l. (diverse genomic species)	Leptospira spp	
Atmospheric methane oxidizers		
Pseudomonas spp.	Trichoderma spp.	Bacillus spp.
Streptomyces sp.	Arthrobacter sp.	Actinomyces sp.
any species of Vibrio spp.	any species of Nitrate reducing bacteria	Plesiomonas sp.
B-cell lymphoma cell lines		
Actinobacteria	Enterobacteria	Myxobacteria
Some fastidious organisms	Organisms not endemic in this country	Rare organisms
Antibiotic-producing actinobacterial non-type strains		
S.cerevisiae	P.chryosporium	
typed virus strains	pure bacterial cultures	cell lines with known background
new Acinetobacter species		
Microalgae?		
Pathogenic strain having biosafety level 3		
Cyanobacteria	bacteriophage	
Shigella boyedii ATCC8700	C.sporogenes	
Thaumarchaeota	"anamnox" clade of Planctomycetales	
Chryseobacterium strains	Not applicable	Not applicable
Nocardia	Streptomyces	Dermatophilus
some nitrifiers	some methanogens	
Bacteria	Archea	Eukariotes in general
Organisms requiring special gas mixtures to grow (microaerophilic methanotrophs for example)		
Bacteriophage	Mycovirus	canophage
Methanogens		
Tuber spp	baculoviruses	
Anoxygenic Phototrophic Bacteria (only limited availability at present)		
Cyanobacteria		
meat associated lactic acid bacteria	meat associated staphylococci	meat associated pseudomonads
xanthobacter	sphingopyxis	hyperthermophilic actinobacteria
Chlorobium	heteronanoflagellates	
selected groups of Archaea		
Bacteriophages		
more than one strain of a species	clinical isolates with detailed information	mutant stains
Certain extremophilic bacteria and fungi (e.g., barophiles or piezophiles)	Certain highly fastidious microorganisms	Microorganisms that cannot be grown on artificial media
Bacillus BNP29		
Recent multi-drug resistant bacteria	Geographically diverse bacteria of relevant species	

Uncultured Lachnospiraceae from the mammalian gut	Segmented-filamentous bacteria from the mammalian gut	Sulphate-reducing bacteria from the mammalian gut
Extremophilic microorganisms	halophilic microorganisms	chemolithotrophic microorganisms
Mycobacteria		
fungi	bacteria	
gut microbiota species	archaea species	
Archaea ammonia oxidizers		
Bacteria	Fungi	Algae
Streptomyces	Staphylococcus	Streptococcus
Cyanobacteria	Endophytic fungi	
segmented filamentous bacteria		
Cancer Cell lines	E. coli strains	Competent E coli strains
archaea		
Acinetobacter		
Thermochromatium tepidum		
parasites (DNA)	virus	
mycobacteria	mycoplasmas	pasteurellaceae
alternaria surely ATXI, ATXII, ATXIII producer		
extremophiles	black fungi	probiotic bacteria

5.8. Annex 8: Overview answers Q28 “New services required by the user community”

Expression vectors for gene products
bioinformatic support for metagenomic data analysis and management
Genomic data
Plasmid construction
guarantee the supplied strain alive
Bioinformatic services with application to ILLUMINA technologies
complete identification
Complete Microbial profile
growth of viruses
Biotechnology: algae fermentation
risk assessment
Immunologic applications
supply different bacteria communities like gut microbiota
Training opportunities concerning bioinformatic software related to research in microbiology
Exchange type strains freely with the depositors and culture collections
Genome sequencing
Genome sequencing also in connection with other projects
proficiency tests/ ring tests!!
Tools which assist in the development of taxonomic expertise outside of mBRC organisations
Been able to search for genome-sequenced strains only
supply of mutants
specific and characterized antibiotic resistance genes (DNA; pos control PCR) or strains
reliable identification of screened MO
1. Susceptibility testing (novel, including natural products and established) antimicrobials/antifungals 2. Mutagenicity tests 3. Management and control of microbial deterioration of archaeological, ecclesiastical and cultural artifacts 4. Indoor air quality monitoring (public health, industry etc)
Quantified suspensions of European Pharmacopoeia reference strains
Array-based detection of multiple pathogens in clinical specimens
very important is THE PRESERVATION. Often strains/species are cited in older literature but not available at present....
Strain authentication
1. Identifying newer novel specific nutrients for microbes like thyroproteins. 2. Identifying novel methods of delivery of the nutrients for example colloidal nutrients 3. Identifying novel methods of coculturing synergistic pair of microbes for example nitrobacter and nitrosomonas 4. Identifying novel methods of converting wet biomass into dry mass with higher shelf life
pcr kits
RNA sequencing, full genome sequencing
indicate different the culture medium for growing
phytoplasma database
-Supply of high quality nucleic acid (DNA, RNA)
Bibliografy
cultivation of difficult microorganisms (oligotrophic environments, extremophiles)
DNA-DNA hybridization, MALDI-TOF, Analysis of quinones, Cellular fatty acid, DNA Composition , full phylogenetic study....
database for On site detection methods
Conservation of complete microbial ecosystems
On-line courses, photographic Bacterial atlas in different media
teaching packs for basis microbiology at diferent academic levels customized isolation of microorganisms
culture collection

access to protein data basis
-strain associated barcode/MLSA sequence information -develop or link to the whole genome sequence
certification of commercial inoculum
PCR identification information down to the strain level
Preservation of numerous strains of the same taxa for genetic diversity studies.
Provision and listing of free material for taxonomic work
Include DNA Bank
Isolation and characterization of microbe
Chromosomal DNA from specific microorganisms (type strains, i. ex.)
Culture moré species that aire still considered unculture
Guaranteed infectiosity
specific culture media for fastidious waterborne pathogens.
gene synthesis
quantified mixtures microorganisms
prices are very high, so that many services but unaffordable prices are useless ...
Service of (personal) culture preservation
possibility of direct contact such as e-mail, for rapid information useful to make specific microbial search and order
production of specific modified microorganisms, already described in the literature but not yet available
molecular taxonomy on isolate supplied at genus level, getting to species or appropriate subspecies level, using fairly common used gene sets
Characterization of antimicrobial resistance mechanisms; plasmid typing
Bacterial genome sequencing: sequencing, genome assembly, and identification and annotation of the open reading frames.
phenotypic characterization
Pathogenecity test of the microorganism/environmental isolates in a animal model system
sequencing service
complete lipid analysis which include specific marker lipids of certain groups, for example glycolipids of archaea
whole genome sequencing of microorganisms
Evaluation of "old" and "new" strains/isolates in terms of pathogenicity etc relevant to their use in biotech industry. Currently there are only few GRAS organisms and it is sometimes difficult to make biotech industries accept to work with new organisms for which they do not know the impact on human health.
sequencing
Developing and maintaining a receptive culture accessioning system accessible at any time of the year is very important.
mutant construction.
qPCR and other quantification methods, community analysis that goes beyond mere DNA sequences, i.e. provides customized results in custom formats.
Provide isolate libraries from complex environmental samples
tailor made GMO organisms ?
It all depends on prices... how much are you going to charge for say, gDNA or cDNA ??? If I have a choice between single culture at 50€ vs. gDNA for 150€, guess which one I will chose if I am on a budget ???!! Services are good, but with our ever shrinking budgets and overhead charges by our own universities, researchers have to be frugal and cut costs.
Whole genome and amplicon based metagenomic sequencing service
identification of metabolites and proteins in (microbial) cell products

5.9. Annex 9: Overview answers Q32 and Q33 “Respondents interested to act as experts and field of expertise”

NON-PROFIT

Country Organisation	Name	e-mail address	Field of expertise
AR - Argentina	Clara Nudel	cnudel@ffyb.uba.ar	microbial physiology and molecular biology
AU - Australia	Natacha Juste-Poinapen	natacha.juste9@gmail.com	Anaerobic growth and syntrophs
AU - Australia	Prof Chris Franco	Chris.franco@flinders.edu.au	Actinobacteria
BE - Belgium	Rob Onderwater	rob.onderwater@materianova.be	extremophiles, metabolism, toxicology, fermentation
BE - Belgium	Martine Maes	martine.maes@ilvo.vlaanderen.be	plant associated microorganisms (bacteria)
BE - Belgium	Erick Vandamme	erick.vandamme@UGent.be	Industrial Microbiology and Biotechnology
BE - Belgium	Taminiau	Bernard.taminiau@ulg.ac.be	Metagenomic analysis of Bacterial and microeukaryote in complex matrices

BE - Belgium	Henri MARAITE	henri.marait@uclouvain.be	phytopathology and crop protection
BE - Belgium	María Isabel Pozo Romero	maribel.pozoromero@bio.kuleuven.be	Microbial ecology, nectar yeasts
BE - Belgium	Berezina Nathalie	nathalie.berezina@materianova.be	industrial biotechnology, biocatalysis
BG - Bulgaria	Dilnora Gouliamova	dilnorag@gmail.com	yeast phylogenetics, taxonomy and ecology
BG - Bulgaria	Penka Petrova	pepipetrova@yahoo.com	
BR - Brazil	Patrícia Costa	patbio24@gmail.com	
BR - Brazil	Verisane Leao	versiane.ufop@gmail.com	Engineering biofertilizers, biopesticides, bacterial volatile organic compounds
CH - Switzerland	Laure Weiskopf	laure.weiskopf@agroscope.admin.ch	microbiology and bacterial fish diagnostic
CL - Chile	Ruben Avendaño-Herrera	ravendano@unab.cl	microbial resources and utilization
CN - China	Bingquan Fan	bqfan@caas.ac.cn	
CN - China	Qingyan Wang	wqyuiuc@gmail.com	Yi Lu

CN - China	Shi Peng	shipeng27@sohu.com	Plant Growth-Promoting Rhinoacteria
CN - China	Wen-Jun Li	wjli@ynu.edu.cn	Microbial systematics
CN - China	Zongjun Du	duzongjun@sdu.edu.cn	bacterial systematics
CN - China	Dong-hui Yan	yandh@caf.ac.cn	forest fungal pathogens
CN - China	chuan xiao	xiaochuanapple@	Bioenergy
CN - China	Li Lei	lilei520acti@qq.com	classification
CN - China	yan zhiying	yanzy@cib.ac.cn	Environmental Microbiology
CN - China	Jinwei Zhang	j.c.zhang@dundee.ac.uk	microoransim, biochemistry etc..
CO - Colombia	Gezira De Avila Montiel	gesira@gmail.com	Biotechnology
CZ - Czech Republic	Pavel Kloucek	kloucek@af.czu.cz	Natural, mainly plant- based, antimicrobials in food, feed, and agriculture.
CZ - Czech Republic	Cenek Novotny	novotny@biomed.cas.cz	fungal physiology, biofilms, biodegradation of organopollutants
CZ - Czech Republic	Vít Ulmann	vit.ulmann@zuova.cz	Mycobacteriology

DE - Germany			Plant-microbe interactions
DE - Germany	Prof. Dr. Joern Kalinowski	Joern.Kalinowski@Cebitec.Uni-Bielefeld.DE	Microbial Genomics
DE - Germany	Marc Stadler	mst12@gbf.de	Mycology and microbiology, natural product research, biotechnology
DE - Germany			
DE - Germany	Elke Lang	ela@dsmz.de	preservation, taxonomy
DE - Germany	Dirk Tischler	dirk.tischler@ioez.tu-freiberg.de	rhodococcus, flavoproteins
DE - Germany	Lothar Kröckel, Dr.	lothar.kroeckel@mri.bund.de	microbiology of meat and meat products
DE - Germany	Thomas Clavel	thomas.clavel@tum.de	
DK - Denmark	Niels-Ulrik Frigaard	nuf@bio.ku.dk	Photosynthetic bacteria
EG - Egypt	mohamed rabie	girss@outlook.com	vaccine
ES - Spain	Susana Rodriguez-Couto	srodriguez@ceit.es	Environmental Biotechnology
ES - Spain	F. Javier Legorburu	jlegorburu@neiker.net	Potato and grapevine viruses

ES - Spain	M ^a INMACULADA Larena	ilarena@inia.es	Plant Pathology, fungi, Biological control
ES - Spain	María M. López	mlopez@ivia.es	Plant pathogenic bacteria bioenergy, biomass transformation, ligninolytic fungi, cellulolytic fungi, yeast in extreme conditions, lignocellulolytic enzymes, microbial biodegradation of biomass
ES - Spain	Aldo GONZÁLEZ	aldo@cbm.csic.es	Food Research (Biotechnology and Industrial Microbiology)
ES - Spain	Raquel Virto	rvirto@cnta.es	DNA replication, DNA repair, Transposition
ES - Spain	Francisco Lopez de Saro	lopezsfj@cab.inta-csic.es	Legionella research in environmental samples; my laboratory control strain collection of isolated pathogens
ES - Spain	Ana M ^a Gimeno Moreno	gimeno_anamor@gva.es	taxonomy, isolation of foodborne bacteria
ES - Spain	Jesús Santos	j.santos@unileon.es	

ES - Spain	Margarita Martínez Medina	marga.martinez@udg.edu	Intestinal Microbiology. Abundance of bacterial indicators. Escherichia coli pathogenicity. Faecalibacterium prausnitzii isolation and characterisation. Large collection of E. coli isolated from the intestinal mucosa of patients with inflammatory bowel disease
ES - Spain	Margarita Martin	margamar@ucm.es	molecular biology Effectiveness of antimicrobial (antibacterial and antifungal) treatments of the materials
ES - Spain	MAITE CANET	mcanet@aitex.es	
ES - Spain	Gema Campos	gema.campos@ictan.csic.es	Food and feed
ES - Spain	Felipe Siverio	fsivros@gobiernodecanarias.org	Plant pathology
ES - Spain	Alfonso Muel	sanitariatellez@gmail.com	
ES - Spain	Lucas del Castillo Agudo	lucas.castillo@uv.es	yeast molecular biology

ES - Spain	Martha E. Trujillo	mett@usal.es	Prokaryotic Systematics - actinobacteria-
ES - Spain	Cristina Pablos Carro	cristina.pablos@urjc.es	microbiological water and food analysis
ES - Spain	Josep Guarro	josep.guarro@urv.cat	taxonomy
ES - Spain	Margarita Aguilera	maguiler@ugr.es	taxonomy, biotechnology
ES - Spain	Pilar Blanco Camba	pilar.blanco.camba@xunta.es	wine yeasts
ES - Spain	SERGIO MARTINEZ	sergio@ugr.es	structural biotechnology
ES - Spain	Antonio Mas	Antonio.Mas@uclm.es	Virology. Protein expression and purification. Viral RNA- dependent RNA polymerases.
ES - Spain	Angela	angela.rubio@uclm.es	Fusarium oxysporum
ES - Spain	Leonardo Romero-Martínez	leonardo.romero@uca.es	Fresh and saltwater treatments for disinfection
ES - Spain	jpascual@cebas.csic.es	jpascual@cebas.csic.es	microbial ecology
ES - Spain	Yolanda Moreno	ymoren@upv.es	detection of waterborne pathogens, mainly

			Helicobacter, by molecular techniques.
ES - Spain	Juan Angel Díaz de Tuesta García	juanangel.diazdetuesta@madrid.org	Veterinary clinical bacteriology
ES - Spain	ricardo.ramos@fpcm.es	ricardo.ramos@fpcm.es	GENOMICS, DNA SEQUENCING
ES - Spain	José Juan Rodríguez	josejuan.rodriguez@uab.cat	
ES - Spain	M. ANGELES CALVO TORRAS	MARIANGELS.CALVO@UAB.CAT	
			Bioactive compounds (nutraceuticals, antitumors, antibiotics); Fast detection methods for food borne pathogens (mPCR, qRTi-PCR, mPCR, biosensor proteins)
ES - Spain	Felipe Lombo	lombofelipe@uniovi.es	
ES - Spain	María de Lourdes Moreno Amador	lmoreno@us.es	Enzyme, nutrition and celiac disease
FI - Finland	Pekka Oivanen	pekka.oivanen@helsinki.fi	culture collection of wood rotting fungi
FI - Finland	Johanna Björkroth	johanna.bjorkroth@helsinki.fi	

FI - Finland	Mr. Petri Susi	pesusi@utu.fi	picornavirus taxonomy, strains
FR - France	Hannu Myllykallio	hannu.myllykallio@polytechnique.edu	target based anti-microbial screening
FR - France	Régis Grimaud	regis.grimaud@univ-pau.fr	interaction of bacteria with non-dissolved organic carbon
FR - France	Lafont	frank.lafont@pasteur-lille.fr	enterobacteriaceae, Imaging Facility for characterization
FR - France	DUPONT Joëlle	joelle.dupont@mnhn.fr	Fungal taxonomy
FR - France	Maupeu Julie	julie.maupeu@u-bordeaux2.fr	wine micorbiology
FR - France	RODRIGUEZ	orodriguez@valagro-rd.com	Anaerobic digestion & microalgae
FR - France	Badet	cecile.badet@u-bordeaux2.fr	oral bacteria
FX - France, Metropolitan	Alyssa Carre-Mlouka	acarre@mnhn.fr	environmental microbiology
GB - United Kingdom	Marcos Quintela Baluja	marcosquintelab@gmail.com	Food-Safety-Antibiotic Resitance Genes

GB - United Kingdom	Eshwar Mahenthiralingam	Mahenthiralingame@cardiff.ac.uk	Cystic fibrosis microbiology, Burkholderia and Pseudomonas, genomics
GB - United Kingdom	Dr Amanda L Jones	amanda.l.jones@northumbria.ac.uk	actinobacterial taxonomy
GR - Greece	Aristea Velegraki	aveleg@med.uoa.gr	MYCOLOGY Medical Mycology, conventional and molecular
GR - Greece	Michael Arabatzis	marabatz@med.uoa.gr	
HR - Croatia	Jasna Hrenovic	jasna.hrenovic@biol.pmf.hr	
HU - Hungary	Istvan Nagy	nagyi@baygen.hu	Propionibacteria; Next- generation sequencing
ID - Indonesia	Dr. Puspita Lisdiyanti	puspita.lisdiyanti@lipi.go.id	Management of Culture Collection
IE - Ireland	James Choiseul	james.choiseul@agriculture.gov.ie	Diagnostics of regulated plant pathogens
IL - Israel	Charles Greenblatt	charlesg@ekmd.huji.ac.il	bioremediation, ancient DNA of pathogens
IN - India	Yogendra Sharma	yogendra@ccmb.res.in	calcium-binding proteins
IN - India	Mahesh Dharne	ms.dharne@ncl.res.in	

IN - India	Prathap K Shetty	pkshalady@yahoo.co.uk	Molecular taxonomy of lactic acid bacteria, characterisation of functional properties
IN - India	Ch Sasikala	sasi449@yahoo.ie	bacterial diversity, description of novel taxa, bioprospecting
IN - India	Dr Subrata K Das	subratkdas@hotmail.com	Microbial discovery and Microbial bioprospecting
IN - India	Srikrishna Subramanian	krishna@imtech.res.in	informatics
IN - India	Yogesh Shouche	yogesh@nccs.res.in	Curator of a Culture Collection
IN - India	Syed G Dastager	syedmicro@gmail.com	Microbial Taxonomy and Systematic
IR - Iran	behnam rasekh	b.rasekh@gmail.com	petroleum biotechnology
IR - Iran	Mohammad Ali Amoozegar	amoozegar@ut.ac.ir; amoozegar@ibrc.ir	Systematic and biotechnology of halophilic bacteria and archaea
IT - Italy	Simone Guglielmetti	simone.guglielmetti@unimi.it	Probiotics
IT - Italy	Patrizia Serratore	patrizia.serratore@unibo.it	seafood hygiene, shellfish diseases

IT - Italy	Luca Cocolin	lucasimone.cocolin@unito.it	food microbiology
IT - Italy	Giulia Massini	giulia.massini@enea.it	microbial ecology
IT - Italy	Gennaro Agrimi	gennaro.agrimi@uniba.it	Metabolic Engineering
IT - Italy	Prof. Sandra Torriani	sandra.torriani@univr.it	Agri-food Microbiology
IT - Italy	Teresa Zotta	teresa.zotta@isa.cnr.it	Metabolism of lactic acid bacteria
IT - Italy	Pasquale Russo	pasquale.russo@unifg.it	lactic acid bacteria
IT - Italy	Massimiliano Fenice	fenice@unitus.it	
IT - Italy	Paola Mattarelli	paola.mattarelli@unibo.it	Bacterial taxonomy
IT - Italy	Patrizia Serratore	patrizia.serratore@unibo.it	seafood and environmental marine bacteria
IT - Italy	Alessio Mengoni	alessio.mengoni@unifi.it	Bacterial genomics
IT - Italy	Carlo Marya Thomas Marobbio	carlomarya.marobbio@uniba.it	heterologous over-expression; phenotype analysis of yeast mutant strains
IT - Italy	Edoardo Carretto	edoardo.carretto@asmn.re.it	Clinical Microbiology, bacteriology, nosocomial infections, molecular

			typing, molecular detection of resistance genes
JP - Japan	Taishi Tsubouchi	t.tsubouchi@jamstec.go.jp	applied microbiology
KR - Korea, South	Jung-Sook Lee	jslee@kribb.re.kr	Taxonomy of bacteria
KR - Korea, South	Long Jin	isacckim@kribb.re.kr	taxonomy, microbial diversity
LU - Luxembourg	Christian PENNY	penny@lippmann.lu	environmental microbiology, genotyping, Campylobacter
MX - Mexico	J Viridiana García Meza	jvgm@uaslp.mx	geomicrobiology
MX - Mexico	Juan Carlos Estrada Mora	jestrada@cinvestav.mx	Culture Collection management
MX - Mexico	Guillermo Aguilar Osorio	gaguilaro@gmail.com	
MX - Mexico	Profra. Jovita Martínez Cruz	jmartine@cinvestav.mx	Culture Collection management
NL - Netherlands	Maria Bergsma-Vlami	m2.bergsma@minInv.nl	Phytobacteriology
NL - Netherlands	B.J.A. Hoeve-Bakker	dienneke.hoeve@rivm.nl	Taxonomy, bacterial identification

NL - Netherlands	Melike Balk	m.balk@uu.nl	Geomicrobiology
NL - Netherlands	Peter Bonants	peter.bonants@wur.nl	plantpathogenic quarantine organisms
PE - Peru	Amparo Zavaleta	azavaletap@unmsm.edu.pe	molecular typing
PL - Poland	Marta Mijs-Krajnik	marta.mijs@uwm.edu.pl	food microbiology
PL - Poland	Stanisław J. Pietr	stanislaw.pietr@up.wroc.pl	biocontrol of plant pathogens, soil microbiology
PT - Portugal	Maria João Fraqueza	mjoaofraqueza@fmv.ulisboa.pt	Food Microbiology
PT - Portugal	Rodrigo Costa	rscosta@ualg.pt	Environmental microbiology, microbial diversity, symbiosis, cultivation of recalcitrant microbial symbionts
PT - Portugal	Celia M Manaia	cmanaia@porto.ucp.pt	bacterial taxonomy and antibiotic resistance in the environment
PT - Portugal	Ligia O. Martins	lmartins@itqb.unl.pt	applied microbiology and enzymology

PT - Portugal	Cristina Cruz	ccruz@fc.ul.pt	AMF and biotransformations of the nitrogen cycle
PT - Portugal	Patrícia Moura	patricia.moura@lneg.pt	Yeasts; Anaerobic bacteria; Microalgae
PT - Portugal	Maria Luisa vieira	vieira@ihmt.unl.pt	Spirochetes
PT - Portugal	Paula Vasconcelos Morais	pvmorais@ci.uc.pt	Bacterial taxonomy; mechanisms on metal resistance
PT - Portugal	Adriano O. Henriques	aoh@itqb.unl.pt	Endosporeforming bacteria (Bacillus/Clostridia)
PT - Portugal	Lúisa Maria Sobreira Vieira Peixe	lpeixe@ff.up.pt	Typing of common pathogenic bacteria (enterococci; E. coli; K. pneumoniae; Acinetobacter baumannii; Samonella enterica) AND Antimicrobial resistance
PT - Portugal	Antonio Correia	antonio.correia@ua.pt	environmental microbiology

PT - Portugal	Catarina Magalhães	cmagalhaes@ciimar.up.pt	Microbia Ecology and Biogeochemistry
RO - Romania	Dinu Mihaela Monica	frommaca@gmail.com	biological control using entomopathogens
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SD - Sudan	Nazik Eltayb Musa Mustafa	nmmustafa@uofk.edu	Food safety
SD - Sudan	M.E. Hamid	mehamid3@gmail.com	Clinicaaly significant aerobic actinomycetes
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US - United States	Michael Siegert	msiegert@engr.psu.edu	methanogenesis, hydrocarbon microbiology, bioelectrical systems
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Respondents that are interested to act as an expert from their sector.

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DE - Germany	Dr. Joachim Bertram	bertram@iba-go.com	proteomics, recombinant protein technologies, cell biology,
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